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Decoding the Face: The role of amygdala on facial behavioural Cues

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requirements of Cardiff Metropolitan University for the
degree of Bachelor of Science

DECLARATION

The following statement must be included, together with a space for signature. This must be signed before the report is submitted to Student Support.

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this dissertation is the result of my own independent investigation under the supervision of my tutor. The various sources to which I am indebted are clearly indicated. This dissertation has not been accepted in substance for any other degree, and is not being submitted concurrently for any other degree.

_____ Lachanas Vlasios, Candidate

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ABSTRACT

Aim: The main aim of this study was to evaluate the Neuro-Linguistic Programming (NLP) assumption concerning the eye-movement in terms of cognitive tasks (narrative memory, imagination, object recognition and spatial attention). Literature up to now, decline NLP as a science based on non-neuropsychological evaluation. Hence, this research clarified cerebrum topography via the cognitive tasks and tried to evaluate the role of amygdala on facial behaviour cues. Amygdala is responsible for emotional processing and it is part of limbic system which via hippocampus activation connects with narrative memory (biographical and autobiographical memory). Hippocampus and amygdala triggers Prefrontal Cortex in terms of executive functioning (i.e decision making, and morality)

Methods: Twenty six (13 male and 13 female) students (healthy participants) were recruited from city unity and 6 female Multiple sclerosis (MS) patients from Policlinic of Evangelismos hospital. The first picture of Thematic Apperception Test (TAT) was used in order to stimulate emotional memories and imagination. More to this, the Edinburgh Handedness Inventory was used for clarifying whether participants were right or left handed. All of the participants were above 18 and they were right- handed. A video camera was used to record the participants' saccades during the experimental tasks.

Results: Healthy population results indicated a partial support to NLP claims concerning the association between saccades and cognitive tasks. More specific, NLP claims of associating right saccades to the imagination task were confirmed, while NLP claims regarding the association between left saccades and recall task were not supported. Further, the bilateral activation of amygdala was confirmed via right saccades associating to left amygdala, reflecting emotional arousal. On the contrary, MS patients' results confirmed the bilateralization of amygdala via the dislocation of emotional functionality. Hence MS patients partially confirmed NLP theory, in terms of cognitive tasks, while in terms of constructing a story, this research findings were not supportive to NLP theory, as prefrontal cortex seems to have a crucial role in this part.

Conclusion: NLP was neuropsychologically evaluated, and it was indicated the crucial role of amygdala and prefrontal cortex. Such results indicate, also the role of saccade reactions in the therapeutic alliance. Yet, further research should be done.

Keywords: NLP, saccades, amygdala, hippocampus, PFC, cognitive tasks.

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Neuro- Linguistic Programming (NLP) is a theoretical framework referring to a communicational structure using specific techniques to alternate human thinking and eye-kinaesthetic behaviour (Duarte, 2016; Sturt et al, 2012). Specifically, NLP, as a cognitive model, suggests the existence of a mind - body system, underling a possible neurobiological association of personal experience, in terms of social knowledge and perception, processed via shallow processing systems: Visual, Auditory and Kinaesthetic (Davis & Davis, 1991). According to the NLP literature, human basic perceptual system derives by a dominant representational system (Primary representational system), interpreting the subjective experience from the environmental stimuli (Wake, 2010).

Accordingly, NLP, supports that shallow processing (vision, sensation and auditory system), and personal cognitions (beliefs, values, and emotions) developed by previous experiences, creates neuropsychological representations of images, sounds and feelings (Walker, 2004). The above-mentioned cognitive system of attitudes, beliefs and emotions system, according to Attitude- Behavior Cognitive (ABC) model (Muran, 1991), leads to an actual behavior. In case of non- verbal communication, the value system of ABC model activates as well for interpreting the movement and the reaction. Specifically, those kinds of movements, based on their intensity, are encoded by independently of specific effectors. More to this, an abstract symbolic level is alternated and a multi-level of controlling facial movement is integrated by mirror neuron activation by intermediating HMOSAIC (Miall, 2003) (see Appendix Figure: Introduction- figure 1). Thus, it is suggested that there is an association among neurological processes (neuro), verbal and non- verbal communication (Linguistic) and behavioural patterns deriving by narrative memory (previous biographic and autobiographic experiences) (Programming). The above statement is interpreted by the NLP practitioner (scientific therapists) who uses this method in order to achieve therapeutic goals (Savardelavar, Bagheri, 2012).

Hence, at this point it is understood that the origins of NLP model as suggested by Korzybski's General Semantics theory, (1958) refer to the neuropsychological connection of body and mind, in which the verbal communication is an extensive analysis of cerebrum circuits and, specifically the connection of Papez circuit (Broca,

Wernicke and arcuate fasciculus) with limbic system and prefrontal cortex (Matsumoto et al., 2004). Such a connection underlines the way that auditory analysis of a phrase regulates emotions and executive functioning. So, the brain localization interact to such a degree that produce experiences and emotional states (Korzybski, 1958), meaning that individuals construct cognitive maps of environmental stimulus that are different from the actual experience (Linder-Pelz, Hall, 2007). In extend to the above, Badler (1979), who is considered a cofounder of this theory, defined NLP as the advanced learning procedure for the decoding and the application of human behavior patterns (Duarte, 2016), which, also, underlines the hippocampus activation.

As far as research on NLP is concerned, initially, literature focused on non-scientific reports that refer to the theoretical background of the specific approach. Particularly, it had been analyzed in terms of its basic development which was based on psychotherapeutic observations conducted on Fritz Perls (who developed Gestalt therapy), Milton Erickson (hypnotherapist) and Virginia Satir (family therapist) therapeutic work (Tosey, Mathison, 2007). To illustrate, Fritz Perl's concept of parts which consists a core characteristic of Gestalts therapy, (Tosey, 2007), Virginias Satir's redefinitions and reframing skill during family sessions (Grinder & Bandler, 1979) and Milton Ericson's hypnotic language patterns, are central to the NLP framework (Williams, 2012). Bandler and Grinder (1979), via the transcription of these therapists work, qualified specific linguistic and behavioural patterns appearing to enchase a potential positive therapeutic outcome (Grinder, Bandler, 1979). More analytically, concerning Perls's influence on NLP, Gestalt theory uses projective techniques such as the empty chair technique, which influences emotional processing of the client's via the integration of cognition in emotional states level (Stein et al., 2014). Further, NLP theory, bases its basic presuppositions on Satir's therapeutic model, in which the challenging of the client's linguistic distortions or generalizations (Habber, 2002; MacLendon, 2000), the association of a positive emotion to a specific stimulus (anchoring) and the potential impact of imagery on client's physiology (future pacing), could produce a positive therapeutic outcome (Bandler et al., 1983; Spitzer, 1992). As far as the Erickson's influence on NLP is concerned, the major characteristic during his therapeutic interventions was the significant focus on client's problem rather than the factors of the problem. Erickson's work suggested that via the sidestepping of conscious by using specific

linguistic patterns, positive changes could occur in client's behaviors, perceptions and emotional states (Grimley, 2016; Mercer, 2015). NLP theorists, based on these identified "effective" methodological patterns, aimed to formulate therapeutic communication models which could be taught and utilized by other therapists with analogous favourable outcome (Karunaratne, 2010). The main instrument of this effort was the method of modeling, which is defined as the adaption of linguistic, behavioral, thought or beliefs patterns of successful therapeutic interventions. Thus, according to NLP framework, modeling of successful therapists, could lead to similar positive therapeutic outcomes (Tosey, Mathison, 2010). In extension to the above, both Perls's and Satir's framework, similar to Roger's person-centered therapy (Hall, 2006), consider the mirroring technique, meaning adopting behavioural characteristics of clients, as vital for the achievement of therapeutic goals such as the establishment of effective therapeutic relationships, trust and empathy (Linder-Pelz & Hall, 2007), which classifies the role of ABC model and mirror neurons activation.

Within NLP framework, mirroring technique might contain gestures, tones, eye movements and breathing imitation (Karunaratne, 2010). Hence, as it can be suggested from the examined therapeutic approaches, mirroring is a technique that includes the potentiality to redefine the therapeutic outcomes (Silani et al., 2013) and it is appearing as an important opportunity to examine basic NLP presuppositions under the neuropsychological perspective. In neuropsychology terms, mirroring, is get activated and also activates or triggers specific neuronal mechanisms (Cook et al., 2014). These neuronal networks are called mirror neurons and are possibly located in the inferior frontal cortex and superior parietal lobe, and get activated via action observation and action operation (Kilner & Lemon, 2013).

NLP Research Literature Review

Even if there is an amount of literature that either supports (Bingley et al., 2010; Stipanic et al., 2010; Wake et al., 2014; Zaharia et al., 2015) or neglects (Heap, 2008; Mann et al., 2012; Wiseman et al., 2012; Witkowski, 2010) NLP, there is a lack of neuro-scientific evidence in both perspectives concerning NLP. For instance, apart from the suggested potential positive impact of NLP interventions on business, learning or sport performance settings literature (Carey et al., 2010; Dondon & Legall, 2006) there is recent scientific research supporting the NLP's positive effects on psychological therapeutic interventions. To illustrate, Stipanic et al (2010), examined NLP interventions effectiveness in 106 cases of psychotherapy clients diagnosed with

psychological difficulties, and results demonstrated a significant decrease of clinical symptoms and increase in the quality of life (Stipanic et al., 2010). Further, Wake et al., (2014) conducted a research among PTSD clients received NLP treatment and findings supported a significant improvement of client's self reported anxiety and depression symptoms (Wake et al., 2014). Additionally, Bingley et al.,(2010) examined the effectiveness of NLP's interventions on patients continually facing claustrophobia during MRI examination and results supported a significant reduction of patient's anxiety levels, that led to the successful examination with the absence of anesthesia (Bingley et al., 2010). Hence, as it can be suggested from the above, NLP is presented as an effective technique for positive therapeutic outcomes, but still NLP bases its effectiveness on presuppositions regarding neuropsychological suggestions meaning the bilateral function of human brain (Grinder, Bandler, 1979) and thus according to scientific method, such suggestions should be tested in neuropsychological terms.

On the other side, non supporting literature to NLP, mainly includes Meta analytical studies of NLP research literature (Heap, 2008; Witkowski, 2010) and experiments designed to test the NLP claims regarding face behavioral cues (Mann et al., 2012; Wiseman et al., 2012). More analytically, Witkowski's (2010) systematic review on NLP research, which concluded that NLP basic tenets are not scientifically supported, based its conclusion on an analysis of papers which were not including neuropsychological perspective (Witkoswki, 2010 see appendix: References) and therefore there is a lack of evidence concerning the outcomes of the above meta analysis. Similarly, Heap (1988) concluded that NLP suppositions are not valid, based on an analysis of papers that in majority were master students dissertations, regarding the NLP claims for facial behavioural cues (eye movements) (Heap, 2008) thus, there is a lack of neuropsychological evidence and also, there is an additional scientific gap about the validity of this criticism that is based on student level papers. More to this, the researches of Mann et al (2012) and Wiseman et al (2012) which both suggested that their results were not supportive to NLP claims, regarding face behavioural cues, did not involve neuropsychological proofs that could support their conclusions concerning NLP theory. Both Wiseman (2012) and Mann (2012) researches, imply designs that are based on incomplete assumptions of NLP, given the fact that participants were asked either to lie or to speak the truth concerning the location of objects in Wiseman et al., (2012) study and regarding future occupation information

in Mann et al., (2012) study. Yet, NLP theory suggests a correlation between eye movements and specific cognitive functions, meaning narrative memory or imagination and it does not examine the truth of an incident as the methodology of Wiseman et al (2012) and Mann et al (2012) researches suggested. Further limitation of Wiseman et al (2012) and Mann et al (2012) experiments, was that participants' face behavioural cues were recorded by a camera and not by an eye tracker device which is designed especially for accurate eye movements' recordings (Duchowski, 2007).

Emotional Memory and Amygdala

As it is interpreted in the above section and according to fMRI models (Catani et al., 2013), limbic system and narrative memory are associated with the communicational system. Somehow, based on the fact that there could be a potential correlation between face behavioral cues and cognitive functions (Grinder & Bandler, 1979) and the functionality of limbic circuit, NLP theory could be a potential method to explain, similarly to Ekman (2004) and Adolf (2001) outcomes, behavioral thinking via facial expressions. Yet, up to now, literature's neuropsychological evaluation of this topic has not been evidenced by fMRI models. Specifically, testing NLP, even nowadays, was being clarified by the prefrontal cortex activation via morality evaluation (lie or truth conditions) (Mann et al., 2012; Wiseman et al., 2012). Thus, in the present paper, it is recommended to examine narrative memory (via an emotional activation task) by placing individual in the center of time, place and associated emotions (Tulving, 2002; Boyer, 2009).

Within scientific literature, it is documented, that long term memory is directly affected by the accounting emotion during the consolidation of the stimuli along with the experiencing emotion during the recalling procedure (Buchanan, 2007; Long et al., 2015; Talarico et al., 2004; Talmi, 2013).

In extent to the above, emotional memory, appear to be dominant among other types of memory in the cerebral activation during the tasks of recalling (such as Rey test) and memory vividness (such as Inc Plots Test and Thematic Apperception Test) (Eschrich et al., 2008; Kensinger, 2007; Murray, 2013), which is supported by a respective amount of research suggesting that emotional arousal escalates the possibility for an enhanced memory of events or objects in terms of vividness or details (Buchanan, 2007; Kazui et al., 2000; Phelps, 2006; Reisberg & Hertel, 2003). Concerning the cerebral areas that evolve in the emotional memory cognitive task,

neuropsychological research suggests that amygdala activation impacts on hippocampus activation (memory) through prefrontal cortex activation and spatial attention, which means that such memory encoding and mechanisms do justify memory consolidation (Hamann, 2001; LaBar, Cabeza, 2006).

Thus, based on neuropsychological indications, amygdala triggers the hippocampus and the prefrontal cortex, which appear to be part of a crucial brain topographical circuit concerning emotional recalling (Hamann, 2001, Labar & Cabeza, 2006; Lonsdorf et al., 2014). Amygdala is located in the medial temporal lobe anterior to the hippocampus (Phelps, Anderson, 1997; Adolphs et al., 1999). In terms of narrative memory localization, literature suggested that it is a crucial locus for the memories that include emotional stimulation via shallow processing (Adolphs et al., 2005; Dolcos et al., 2004; Lezak, 2012; McGaugh, 2004).

To illustrate, Hamann (2001) proved that amygdala enhance declarative memory, as it is responsible for the analysis and the perception of both positive and negative emotional stimuli by the formation of consolidation and encoding procedures (Hamann, 2001). Further, amygdala intermediates emotional learning facets and accommodates memory activities in other regions such as the hippocampus and prefrontal cortex (Lebar, Cabeza, 2006). More to this, according to Murty et al (2010), amygdala perceive neurotransmitter's signals by visual modules, prefrontal and parietal cortices in such way that enhances attention, semantic elaboration and perceptual processing which consecutive enhances emotional memory (Murty et al., 2010).

Additionally to scientific research, proposing amygdala's primary role on the processing of emotional stimuli (Adolphs et al., 2002; Shaw et al., 2005), there is neuropsychological evidence underlying the bilateral function of amygdala, during the processing cognitive tasks of memory and emotion (Canli et al., 2000). More to this, a meta-analysis of 54 fMRI and PET model studies conducted by Baas et al., in 2004, supported that the left amygdala is more often activated than the right amygdala, which clarifies the amygdala bilateralization (Baas et al., 2004). Such a result indicates the role of Hemispheric Encoding Retrieval Asymmetry (HERA) theory in the cerebrum functionality via localization asymmetry.

Hemispheric Encoding Retrieval Asymmetry (HERA) Model and Memory

HERA model refers to hemispheric encoding/retrieval asymmetry. Tulving et al (1994), based on Positron Emission Tomography (PET) studies, proposed a brain lateralization model regarding memory. According to this model, brain's left and right prefrontal lobes, consist a neuronal network that sub serves episodic memory with each hemisphere having a different role. More specific, left hemisphere is critical to encoding into long term memory while right hemisphere is critical to retrieval from long term memory (Tulving et al., 1994). Expanding the HERA model application in memory domain, it has been proved that activation of one hemisphere alternates the opposite side of somatic reactions (Propper et al., 2013). In terms of episodic memory encoding, left prefrontal cortex (PFC) is more involved than right PFC, while in episodic memory retrieval, right PFC is more involved than left PFC (Habib et al., 2003). Recently, it has been claimed that this description does not hold for non-verbal materials (Johnson et al., 2003). Nowadays, it is sufficient that this PFC activation is sufficient for both verbal and non-verbal materials (Habib et al., 2003).

Thus, comparing HERA theory (which supports a critical involvement of right hemisphere during memory retrieval), to the NLP communicational model, (which supports the existence of specific eye kinesthetic behaviors-Left saccade) during memory retrieval task (Grinder & Bandler, 1979), it seems that HERA is a potential model to examine scientifically, the NLP claims regarding specific eye kinesthetic behavior.

Lateralization Models of Amygdala

In extension to the HERA model claims, regarding the encoding and retrieval processes of emotionally neutral memories, there is additional neuropsychological research, suggesting bilateral amygdala function depending from the kind of the executing cognitive processes (memory, attention and emotion) (Troiani et al., 2004; van den Bulk et., 2014; Young & Williams, 2015;). Specifically, Wright and colleagues (2001) and Baeken and associates (2014), suggested distinctive information processing roles for right and left amygdala. Right amygdala is, instantly, activated by dynamical emotional stimulus detection, while left amygdala is presenting enhanced activation during stimulus evaluation (Wright et al., 2001; Baeken, 2014). Still, the lateralization models of amygdala region are divided into two main axis: The axon which screens the differences in amygdaloid region hemispheres, based on memory retrieval and encoding processes (Bernstein et al.,

2002; Markowitch, 1999; Sergrerie et al., 2005; Yamamoto et al., 2017) and the axon evaluating the activation of amygdala- lateralization via the emotional valence stimulus (positive or negative) (Anderson & Phelps, 2001; Canli et al., 2002; Dyck et al., 2011; Hamman & Mao, 2002; Killgore & Yurgelun-Todd, 2001; Schneider et al., 1997; Zald & Pardo, 1997).

Concerning scientific research examining amygdala lateralization in terms of emotional memory (encoding and retrieval processes), equivalently to the NLP Theory, Markowitch (1999) supported a correlation between right hemispheric activation (amygdala) and retrieval of emotional memories (Markowitsch, 1999). More to this, Bernstein et al., in 2002, conducted a neuropsychological study supporting that there is an association between enhanced activation of left amygdala and memory encoding (Bernstein et al., 2002). Similar to the above, Yamamoto and associates (2017), conducted a research among participants with early life stress (ELS) demonstrating significant higher right- amygdala- activation after recalling sad memories (Yamamoto et al., 2017). Hence, Markowitsch (1999), Bernstein et al (2002) and Yamamoto et al (2017) studies clearly supported a significant correlation between emotional memory retrieval and right amygdala activation. Conversely, Sergrerie et al. (2005), conducted an fMRI study examining amygdala in memory settings demonstrating that during encoding there was a right hemisphere activation while during retrieval there was a left hemisphere activation (Sergerie et al., 2005).

Furthermore, a considerable amount of research (Canli et al., 2002; Killgore & Yurgelun-Todd, 2001; Schneider et al., 1997; Zald & Pardo, 1997), suggests a distinctive engagement of right and left amygdala during emotional processing (Sergerie et al., 2008), supporting a left lateralized preference of amygdala when it comes for account an emotional stimulus (positive or negative). More to this, results of Anderson and Phelps (2001) study supported that the perception of aversive words depends specifically on the left amygdala (Anderson & Phelps, 2001). In a similar vein, Hamman and Mao (2002) conducted an fMRI study concluding that positive and negative emotional words result in left amygdala activation (Hamman & Mao, 2002). More recently, Dyck et al. (2011), conducted a neuropsychological study supporting enhanced left amygdala activation during negative emotional valence (Dyck et al., 2011). Additionally to the previous studies which implied a left lateral preference of amygdala during the processing of aversive or positive stimuli, there is research evidence illustrating sex differences regarding brain lateralization in emotional

processing, fact that should be further examined (Cahil et al., 2001; Victor et al., 2017; Wrase et al., 2003).

Therefore, as it can be suggested from the scientific evidence regarding bilateral function of amygdala and by the critical role of amygdala in emotional memories retrieval in collaboration with the prefrontal cortex and hippocampus (Buchanan, 2007; Phelps, 2004), the scientific models concerning the hemispheric specificity of amygdala present the potentiality to examine, via the neuropsychological perspective, the NLP claims regarding individual's eye movements during the memory retrieval phase. Additionally, findings of Haj and colleagues regarding eye movements, supported that bigger amount of saccades with lower duration is produced, comparing emotional memories to neutral memories, (El Haj et al., 2017). Such an evidence underlines the need for examining a potential existence of a neuropsychological prioritisation order between memory cognitive tasks (retrieval or encoding) and emotional processing, which might be reflected on individuals facial behavioural cues (eye movements).

NLP and Eye Movements

According to the NLP model, specific eye movements could be viewed as an indicator of occurring cognitive process (Grinder & Bandler, 1979). More specific, concerning right – handed individuals, left saccades indicate a memory processing (retrieval), while right saccades indicate the cognitive process of mental constructing (imagination) (Wiseman et al., 2012). Bandler and Grinder (1979), supported this claim, similar to Kocel et al. (1972) psychological research, based on the brain hemisphericity theory (Grinder & Bandler, 1979; Kocel et al., 1972), which is a debatable model, proposing that a part of the human population has a predisposition on processing information with right or left cerebral hemisphere irrespectively of the conditions, based on the assumption that each hemisphere has different information processing capabilities (Mendoza, 2011).

Visual Eye Movements

During the process of vision, eyes scan the environmental stimuli via saccadic movements (Findlay & Walker, 1999) aiming individuals to construct the modularity maps of the environmental settings (Borji & Itti, 2014). Further, according to Bridgeman (2012), eyes operate as a directive mechanism for the attention as well as a form of emotional expression (Bridgeman, 2012). In terms of definition, saccade is the accelerated reposition of both eyes (Bulling et al., 2009) that occur periodically

and concurrently with eyes fixation (pauses over localities of interest) (Salvucci & Goldberg, 2000). Though, goal directed saccades are divided into two types: A. Reactive visually guided saccades, occurring consequently to the sudden presentation of a new stimulus and B. Internally triggered or voluntary saccades, occurring in response to internal goals and motivations (Broerse et al., 2001; Pellison et al., 2010). Hence, frequency of the saccadic eye movement varies depending from individual differences or executing tasks; from one saccade every several seconds up to three saccades per second (Kowler, 2011), with voluntary saccadic eye movements being ordinarily larger than 250 ms (Pellison et al., 2010).

Non Visual Eye Movements and Cognitive Neuroscience

Non visual eye movements are defined as saccades that are occurred once an individual do not targets a visual stimulus but indigenous cognitive processes such as thinking or imaging are attended (Ehrlichman & Barrett, 1983). This is supported by a cognitive psychological research suggesting that the direction of saccade during cognitive processing, possibly, demonstrates the lateralization of the inherent cerebral activity (Kinshurnc, 1972).

NLP claims concerning the relationship between facial behavioural cues (Eye movements) and cognition is not novel. To the contrary, cognitive neuroscience, has further examined eye movement's topic in order to extract conclusions regarding the function of the human brain (Leigh & Zee, 2015). The larger part of the research, examined a possible correlation between eye movements and brain hemisphericity during specific cognitive tasks (Beaumunt et al., 1984). The methodology of this research field, mainly included data collection of eye kinaesthetic behaviours recorded in digital cameras or eye trackers (Hutton, 2008; Liversedge & Findlay, 2000; Spivey & Geng, 2001).

Initially, researchers focused on the possible correlation between lateral eye movements and brain asymmetrical hemispheric activation, providing some empirical evidence (Bakan, 1969; Gur, 1975; Kocel et al., 1972; Meskin & Singer, 1974; Walker et al., 1982; Weiten, 1973). Yet, the majority of the later researches provided contradicted results (Hugdahl, 1984) in different directions concerning brain hemisphericity theory, such as personality characteristics or negative and positive emotions (Beaumunt et al., 1984; De Gennaro & Violani, 1988; Paus, 1996; Sackeim et al., 1984; Takeda & Yoshimura, 1969; Tomer & Mintz, 1980), that either were

rejecting or were unable to stabilize the reliability of this model (Ehrlichman & Weinberger, 1978; Hatta, 1984).

In recent years, a respectful amount of scientific research has re-examined the eye movement behaviour as a potential indicator of executing cognitive processes and results supported a relationship between eye movements and cognitive tasks (Borji & Itti, 2014; Droll et al., 2005; Hayhoe & Ballard, 2005; Henderson et al., 2013; Orquin & Loose, 2013; Peterson & Beck, 2011). Specifically, Burke et al. (2003) conducted a study regarding the correlation between eye movements and cognitive tasks with results implying that eye movements were reflecting an ongoing thinking process (Burke et al., 2003). More to this, according to Vrij et al. (2015), memory retrieval process generates accumulative non-visual saccadic eye movement activity (Vrij et al., 2015). Thus, nowadays, it is scientifically accepted that cognitive processes such as memory, have a significant impact on saccadic eye movements (Hutton, 2008) during the execution of non visual cognitive tasks (Ehrlichman et al., 2007). Hence non visual eye movements could be counted as an indicator of an inner brain activity.

Eye Movement Desensitization and Reprocessing (EMDR) Therapy

The relationship between eye movements and cognitive tasks, has been further examined within clinical applications settings (Barrowcliff et al., 2004; Cooper et al., 2017; Shapiro & Maxfield, 2002). To illustrate, Eye Movement Desensitization and Reprocessing (EMDR) therapy, an arguable therapeutic model suggested for posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD) (Davidson & Parker, 2001), utilizes bilateral eye movements for stimulating right and left hemispheres of the brain, aiming the desensitization of patient's traumatic memories (Stickgold, 2002). Cerebral information processing, is reiterated by the use of balanced stimulation of cerebral hemispheres via eye movements, interspersed by the traumatic memory's retrieval and its behavioural, cognitive and biological components (Rimini et al., 2016). EMDR, relies its theory on a biological explanation, supporting that certain bilateral eye movements during the therapeutic session, creates such neural activity in the frontal lobes (Oh & Choi, 2007) and enhanced left hemispheric activation (Pagani et al., 2011), which consecutive results in a positive therapeutic affect on the patient's working memory (Barrowcliff et al., 2004), concentration and emotional regulation (El Khoury-Malhame et al., 2017; Shapiro et al., 2017).

Hence, taking in account the scientific research which examines the role of eye movements in terms of memory (Orquin & Loose, 2013; Propper & Christman, 2008)

and emotion (Onderdonk & van den Hout, 2016; Parker et al., 2017) within experimental (Burke et al., 2003; Propper & Christman, 2008) and therapeutic frameworks (Barrowcliff et al., 2004; Little et al., 2017; Pagani et al., 2011), underlines the possibility of a neural circuit including brain regions such as prefrontal cortex, hippocampus and amygdala, that is utilized or utilizes facial behavioural cues in order to reflect the executing cognitive tasks or to stimulate affective therapeutic neural activation.

Multiple Sclerosis (MS)

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is a neurodegenerative disease characterized by lesions' in the central neural system, in which the topography of lesions affects certain cognitive functions (Calabrese et al., 2011). In terms of MS symptomatology, it is consisted by a wide range of neuropsychiatric, executive cognitive functionality and sensory-motor symptoms, affected by fatigue symptoms (Polman et al., 2010). According to McDonalds criteria (2010), it has 3 types of severity Relapsing Remitting MS (RRMS), which within 25 years, in the 90% of patients transform into a Secondary-Progressive disease course (SPMS), which is characterized by steady neurological decline (Milo & Miller, 2014). About 10% of MS patients also exhibit a disease course with steady decline in neurological function without recovery and are classified as primary progressive MS (PPMS). (Henry et al, 2009). According to research on topics of cognitive impairments, executive function, perception of emotions and spatial attention are the most affected cognitive functions. Out of this, it is supported that women perform better than men (Henry et al, 2009; Krause et al., 2013).

Aim and Experimental Hypothesis

Based on the combination of the above models and the association of the above theoretical frameworks, the present paper aimed to examine the relationship between face behavioral cues and memory narratives, in terms of memory cognitive task and emotion cognitive task comparing to the NLP assumptions. Therefore, it is hypothesized that the imagination- cognitive task of narrative memory activation will be reflected by a right saccade according to NLP theory. Also, recall of object location, object recognition and emotional recall will be reflected via a left saccade. Last, based on the amygdala lateralization models, three hypotheses were raised up. Referring to amygdala lateralization based on emotional valance, the left amygdala activation (positive or negative emotions and contents) will be reflected by a right

saccade. Referring to amygdala lateralization based on recall, the left amygdala activation will be reflected by a right saccade. In the contrary to the above, the right amygdala activation during recall will be reflected by a left saccade.

CHAPTER 2

METHODOLOGY

Participants

Health population

For the purpose of this study, 26 participants were recruited from City Unity college. Participants were recruited via the snowball effect. All participants were students which were informed from both lecturers and students that had already participated in the study. Female participants were 13 and male 13 individuals as well. The inclusion criterion was to be over 18 and had no diagnosis of depression and other psychological disorder.

MS population

6 female participants were recruited via evaggelismos hospital-polyclinic MS department. The sample was a stratified one, as the inclusion criterion was to have lesions in prefrontal cortex, amygdala and hippocampus. Based on Krause et al., (2013) and Henry et al., (2009) outcomes, only women with RRMS were included in the sample size. All of them were above 18 and the age range was 22 up to 37 years old. Participants were matched to the healthy population via their educational level.

Design

An explanatory sequential mixed-methods study was conducted (Morse, 2003) including semi-structured interview and Post hoc analysis. Quantitative and qualitative data were equivalently emphasized. Qualitative data was gathered for exploring the expressed themes (emotional arousal) by participants and then quantitative data was collected (Saccades during tasks and raised themes) in order to discuss the relationships found on qualitative data (exploratory sequential research). Data was gathered from two groups of participants (Healthy population and MS population), performing a number of tasks including 3 recalling tasks and 1 narrative task (story telling). Based on the given stimulus (TAT card), narrative task was analyzed via the Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA).

Materials

For the purpose of this study, an information sheet and consent form was given to participants for information and signing. Further, in order to clarify the hemispheric asymmetry theory assumption, the Edinburgh Handedness Inventory and Apperception Test were used.

Edinburgh Handedness Inventory (Oldfield, 1971): It is a ten items questionnaire, inquiring participants to imply their preferred hand for using in daily activities. It is measuring whether activities (eg. Writing, throwing) require left, right or both hands. In scoring terms, responses are expected to provide a laterality outcome, ranging from -100 (strong left) to +100 (strong right). Negative scores imply a left-handed preference while positive score imply a right handed preference (Mazoyer et al., 2014). The validity of the test is 0.89 (Veale, 2014).

Thematic Apperception Test (TAT): It was used as a stimulus for the experiment's tasks of narrative (story telling), emotions recall, object recognition recall, object location recall and expressed emotion. TAT is a reliable clinical tool (Serfass & Sherman, 2013) developed by Murray (1943), evolving the story telling task after participants have been provided provocative and ambiguous pictures (Shahbazzadegan et al., 2016). In this manner, TAT collates emotional memory with images (Aronow et al., 2013). Literature suggest that if a research is about to use a small amount of TAT- pictures, then the only picture that participants should be provided with is the first picture of the TAT (the child with the violin) as reflects high emotional arousal. The story scores from 1 to 11 in concern to the amount of imagery-achievements (Tuerlinckx et al, 2002).

Further, for the recording of the participant's saccadic behaviour, a digital video camera (Sony HDR-CX116E) was positioned in front of the participants, at eye level and the distance between participant's eyes and camera's lens was approximately 175 cm. Camera's technical characteristics include: Video resolution: 1.35 MP, Lens aperture f/1.8-2.2, optical zoom: 25x, filter size: 30mm and maximum focal length: 62.5 mm.

Procedure

This project was approved by Cardiff Metropolitan University Psychology Research Ethics Committee, City Unity College Psychology Research Ethics Committee and Evaggelismos Polyclinic Ethics Committee (see appendix I: Cardiff Metropolitan University Psychology Research Ethics Committee and Evaggelismos Folder). All participants signed written consent forms (see appendix II: Information sheet and Consent Form).

Healthy population group

The study was conducted in the City U College's experiment lab. The experimenter was initially visiting classes informing professors for the study. Then, professors were informing students that after the end of the class, they could find the researcher in the lab and set an appointment. All participants were tested individually. Each participant arriving in the lab was receiving the information sheet and then he or she was signing the consent form and completing the Edinburgh Handedness Inventory. Any confusion issue concerning the scales or items was explained. Each participant was asked to sit in a chair in front of a desk. All participants were told that the experiment was studying facial behavioural cues and memory. A digital video camera (Sony HDR-CX116E) was positioned in front of the participant at eye level. The camera was placed on the desk in a manner that the entire face of participant was clearly viewable. The distance between participant's eyes and camera's lens was approximately 175 cm. The only guideline concerning the participant's position included that their face should be visible by the camera and that they would be reminded of this in case of moving out of the camera's recording range. Further, the examiner did not reveal anything regarding eye movements' recordings. Participants were given the individual appropriate time in each case, for responding to the tasks. In total, participants were asked to perform 4 tasks in the apparent order: 1. Story telling (Narrative) task, 2. Recall of emotions and thoughts task, 3. Object recognition recall task and 4. Object location recall task. TAT card was presented to the participants for 1 minute and just before the beginning of interview, was gently removed. As each participant was performing in each task, eye movements were being recorded. First task was the narrative task, in which participants, were asked to tell a story based on the card they saw (TAT). Second task was the emotional recall task, in which participants were

asked to recall the potential feelings or thoughts of the Card's character (Child). Third task was the object recognition recall task, in which participants were asked to recall the kind of card character's clothing. Fourth task was the object location recall task, in which participants were asked to recall whether there was an additional object within the picture. Collected data of the experiment was including saccades just before participants perform the tasks, and further, saccades just before the expression of a world containing emotional arousal (e.g. sadness, pity, punishment, happiness, optimism) derived from the thematic analysis.

Concerning the interview's coding, each one of the 32 interviews was video recorded and then it was analyzed via an eye movement's log which was registering performed saccades in association to the experiment's tasks (narrative, recall, and expressed emotion). Similar to Vrij and colleagues (2015), registered saccades were those which were performed in the period between the interviewer finishing question and the participant beginning answering the question. Once within NLP literature, there is not any particular referral concerning the duration of saccades that could be considered as informative to the topic (Cognitive tasks) (Wiseman et al., 2012), this study investigated the saccades generated just before performing the tasks of story telling (narrative), recall and emotional expression (occurring themes of thematic analysis).

MS population group

MS participants were approached in Polyclinic hospital, at the MS department of Evaggelismos. The office 512 was offered to the researcher, in order to conduct the experiment. The neuropsychologist of the Polyclinic in agreement with the Doctors of the polyclinic, were informing the patients regarding the experiment and they were sending them for additional info in the office. Each patient was given the information sheet, receiving any other required verbal information and after they were signing the consent form. Once they agreed to participate in the experiment the same procedure with healthy population was occurred. In any case, both the neuropsychologist of the department (who is researcher's supervisor as well) and the clinical psychologist of the department were there in case of distress. Yet, not such problems were occurred.

Method of Analysis

Statistical analysis occurs two types of research method; Qualitative and quantitative. Qualitative analysis is performed by themes in each task. Every theme is associated with saccades during the ongoing process of the interview, recording even the eyes kinaesthetic behaviour up to three saccades per second.

IPA analysis was used for the coding of content themes, which aims researchers to further explore efficiently, the individual's environmental experience (Smith et al., 1993) and a master table of themes occurred (Biggerstaff & Thompson, 2008) including emerged categories relative to the topic (Negative-Positive content-emotion). For the analysis of the present paper results a SPSS program vs 23 was used. More to this, frequencies were observed via descriptive statistics, chi-square analyses were performed in order to clarify: A. The association of NLP claims concerning eye kinaesthetic behaviour in conditions of recalling and constructed stimuli. B. The association of saccades and lateralization models of amygdala in terms of recalling and arousal. Last for analysing the hypothesis in depth, Mann-Whitney and Kruskal Wallis tests were used for testing differences. Out of this, as far as Multiple Sclerosis (MS) sample is concerned, three one-sample t-tests were performed in order to clarify the relationship between cognitive tasks and eye movements.

CHAPTER 3

RESULTS

Qualitative Results

For the purpose of the study, semi-structural interview type was used. 4 questions were raised up: A: Could you please tell me a story concerning the picture that you just saw? B: What might the child was feeling or thinking? C: What was the child wearing? and D: Except from the violin and the notebook, what else was existing in the desk?. In concern of the answer given in these questions, specific themes aroused in terms of negative and positive (arousal) emotion and content. In a more analytical manner, the bellow labels were screened by two psychologists and there was a total agreement in the themes analysis by both of them (see appendix III: Example of Qualitative Analysis and Evidence Box). First, interviews were transcribed in electronic form. Then the researcher conducted an in vivo coding method concerning the syntax and words. Via the coding method, communalities were developed. Once codes were categorised by both the researcher and the supervisor of this theses, separately, the themes were compared to one another. AS Saldana in 2015 suggested, subcategories have been compromised into a larger theme. Based on these procedures an axial coding method was performed certifying 4 triangulated main themes (Saldana, 2015).

Theme 1: Negative emotions including Sadness (also expressed as affliction and unhappiness) and fear. It was observed that most of the participants have expressed negative thoughts concerning the imagination (story telling) task.

Imagination: Ehm i believe that it was a little boy who was learning playing the violin and he was seemed very focus on this, ehm and i think and i think he was sad because he could not play the song given from the teacher and he was thinking the steps for doing it right.

Such an outcome proves theories of Cognitive Emotional Therapeutic approach in appreciation to automatic thinking (Beck, 1995).

Theme 2: Positive emotions including happiness. Two participants expressed positive emotions.

Participant A expressing happiness: Ehm he might ehm was feeling that he was feeling joy or he was feeling that learning the notes is something that he has to do in order to accomplish to do the thing he really likes to play violin.

Participant B expressing happiness: ehm possibly a bit happy because he finished ehm, the choir, the song played, anything might a bit proud, stress relief this.

This could be compromised to personality types, reflecting the optimistic type and the coping strategies (Prati & Pietrantonio, 2009).

Theme 3: Negative content including linguistic expressions such as poverty, worry, lack of confidence, prohibition, obligation, difficulties, trouble, grounded, complaint, nostalgia, failure, restriction, doubt, unwillingness, pressure, trapped, disappointment, difficulties, confusion, loneliness, one parent, low income, melancholy, oppression and not feeling loved. The majority of the participants expressed linguistically the positive content of their thinking using the word “disappointment”.

Negative content-disappointment: I saw one disappointment as he looks the organ this, one failure.

Emotional coping strategies could be the answer in such observation, underlining the conflict of an unknown and sudden situation in terms of automatic thinking and by approaching the “fight or flight” state (Leonard & Myint, 2009).

Theme 4: Positive content including linguistic expressions such as desire, accomplishment, excitement, focus, determination optimism, proud, stress relief, love partner, enjoy, beautiful story, positive change, future planning, support, interest, good student, creativity, knowledge and admiration. The majority of the participants expressed linguistically the positive content of their thinking using the word “desire”

Positive content-desire: He wanted very much to learn the violin and he finally managed to gather the money and buy it and it is in front of him.

This seems to be associated with expectations of the way that a conflict could be resolved, proving the need that individuals have for an instant and successful solution to each conflict.

Quantitative results

A Shapiro Wilks test was employed in order to examine whether the observed distribution fit the normal distribution (Table 1). Results indicated that the observed distribution does not fit the normal distribution. Specifically, except the total number of negative content (S-W (11)= 0.897, p= 0.171), stimuli content (S-W (11)= 0.889, p= 0.135) and eye- movement content (S-W (11)= 0.890, p= 0.138), that fit normal distribution the rest variables do not fit normal distribution ($p < 0.05$). Therefore, non-parametric test will be employed for testing the present study's hypotheses (see Appendix IV: Test of Normality).

Table 1: Test of Sample Normality

Variables	Shapiro-Wilk	df	p value
Sex	0,625	11	0,000
Total number of expressed positive content	0,734	11	0,001
Total number of expressed negative content	0,897	11	0,171
Eye Movement Direction Before Narrative	0,572	11	0,000
Stimuli Content	0,889	11	0,135
Emotions	0,724	11	0,001
Emotional thoughts direct Recall amygdale	0,774	11	0,004
NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade	0,625	11	0,000

NLP Assumption Recall-Left saccade	0,649	11	0,000
Object recognition direct recall	0,786	11	0,006
hippocampus			
Object location direct recall PFC	0,786	11	0,006
NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade	0,649	11	0,000
Existing cues	0,649	11	0,000
Eye movement for emotions	0,769	11	0,004
Eye movement content	0,890	11	0,138
NLP Assumption Construct-Right	0,572	11	0,000
Saccade			
Amygdala Emot Model 1 Assumption	0,572	11	0,000
Left Arousal(POS/NEG)-Right			
Saccade			
Amygdala Cont Model 1 Assumption	0,649	11	0,000
Left Arousal(POS/NEG)-Right			
Saccade			
Amygdala Q1 Model 1 Assumption	0,572	11	0,000
Left Activation Recall-Right Saccade			
Amygdala Q1 Model 1 Assumption	0,625	11	0,000
Right Activation Recall-Left Saccade			

Frequencies were examined via descriptive statistics in orders to clarify the sex of participants, the saccade orientation per task and per content and emotional arousal. The sample included equal number of men (13 individuals) and women (13 individuals). As far as arousal in terms of emotion and content, 12 out of 26 were emotionally aroused in both contexts while the rest expressed neutral emotional reaction. The 73% of our sample reflected a right saccade right before story telling

task (Imagination) confirming the NLP assumption in terms of story telling task reflecting right saccade. As far as content context is concerned the 48.5% expressed both negative and positive content, while 23.1% expressed positive, 23.1% negative and 15.4% neutral content. In terms of emotions expressed in story telling task, the 53% expressed neutral, 34.6% negative, 7.7% positive and 3.8% both negative and positive emotions. In task 1, which reflects the activation of narrative memory concerning eye movements, 42.3% reflected a left saccade (L), 38,8% a fixation (C) and 53.8% reflected a right saccade (R). In this task the 42.3% had confirmed NLP assumption about left saccade (L) reflection. In task 2 which applies the object recognition memory patterns, the 50% reflected a right saccade (R), while the 65.4% did not confirm the NLP assumption in terms of left saccade (L) reflecting the object recalling task. In task 3 concerning object location memory, the 57.7% reflected a right saccade (R), and the 61.5% did not confirmed NLP assumption in terms of left saccade (L) reflecting the object location recalling task. As far as eye movement and emotion is concerned 53 % expressed neutral emotion reflecting central saccade (fixation) and 26.9 % expressed negative emotions and reflected a right saccade. In terms of eye movements and content, the 46.2% expressed a negative content, reflecting right saccade, 15.4% expressed a positive content and had left saccade, while 15.4% had neutral content and reflected a central saccade (fixation) (see appendix V: Frequencies for Healthy Population).

A non- parametric chi square test was conducted in order to examine whether the imagination- cognitive task of narrative memory activation will be reflected by a right saccade according to NLP theory. Results indicated that NLP assumption reflects a specific saccade ($\chi^2(2)= 5.538, p<0.05$). Specifically, 19 out of 26 participants reflected a right saccade, 6 a left and 1 a central, confirming NLP assumptions. So, Right saccade was proved to be associated with imagination- story telling task (see Appendix VI: Hypothesis 1).

In extent to the first hypothesis two more analyses were conducted for examining in depth the above outcome. A Mann Whitney test was performed in order to examine whether there was a significant difference between participants that had an emotional arousal (amygdala activation) and those that did not expressed an emotional arousal (no expression of emotion/ neutral reaction) in positive and in negative content.

Results indicated that there is a significant difference between participants that had an emotional arousal (amygdala activation) and those that did not expressed an emotional arousal (no expression of emotion/ neutral reaction) in negative content ($U=45$, $p<0.05$). Specifically, the mean rank of participants expressed emotional arousal in negative content was 16,75 while the mean rank of those who did not express emotional arousal was 10,71 (see Appendix VI: Hypothesis 1- extended Hypothesis a).

A Kruskal Wallis was, also, performed in order to evaluate the effect of positive or negative content on saccades. Results indicated that there is an effect of content on the saccade. Specifically, positive content ($\chi^2(6)= 7.62$, $p< 0.05$) reflect a central saccade (mean rank= 19), while negative content ($\chi^2(6)= 5.54$, $p< 0.05$) reflect a right saccade (mean rank= 14.29) (see table 2) (see Appendix VI: Hypothesis 1- extended Hypothesis b).

Table 2: Mean ranks of saccade according to Content's Emotion.

Table 2: Mean ranks of saccade according to Content's Emotion.

	Eye movement content	N	Mean Rank
	Center-Positive	2	19.00
	Center-Negative	1	3.50
	Right-Positive	1	12.00
	Right-Negative	12	10.67
Total number of expressed positive content	Left-Positive	4	14.00
	Left-Negative	1	3.50
	Both Right and Left-Positive	1	12.00
	Total	22	
	Center-Positive	2	8.50
	Center-Negative	1	10.00
	Right-Positive	1	5.50
	Right-Negative	12	14.29
Total number of expressed negative content	Left-Positive	4	7.25
	Left-Negative	1	10.00
	Both Right and Left-Positive	1	10.00
	Total	22	

A non-parametric chi square test was conducted to examine whether the narrative memory recall and NLP assumptions will be reflected by a specific saccade according to NLP theory. Results indicated that narrative memory recall reflect a right saccade ($\chi^2(2)= 10.692, p<0.05$). Specifically, 14 out of 26 participants reflected a right saccade, 11 a left and 2 a central. As far as NLP assumptions are concerned they are not confirmed by emotional recall($\chi^2(1)= 0.615, p>0.05$). Results indicate that 11 out of 26 participants had a left saccade as NLP claims. Thus, right saccade was proved to be associated with narrative memory (see Appendix VII: Hypothesis 2-task 1).

Also, a non-parametric chi square test was conducted to examine whether the object recognition via recall task and NLP assumptions will be reflected by a specific saccade according to NLP theory. Results indicated that there is no association of saccade to the task ($\chi^2(2)= 4.962, p=0.096$) and NLP assumptions are not confirmed by this task ($\chi^2(2)= 2.462, p=0.117$). Only, 9 out of 26 had a left saccade as NLP claims. Yet, 13 participants had a right saccade reflecting object recognition (see Appendix VII: Hypothesis 2-task 2).

A non-parametric chi square test was conducted to examine whether the object location recall/ spatial attention and NLP assumptions will be reflected by a specific saccade according to NLP theory. Results indicated that spatial attention recall reflect a right saccade ($\chi^2(2)= 11.615, p<0.01$). Specifically, 15 out of 26 participants reflected a right saccade, 10 a left and 1 a central. As far as NLP assumptions are concerned they are not confirmed by emotional recall($\chi^2(1)= 1.385, p=0.239$). Results indicate that 10 out of 26 participants had a left saccade as NLP claims. Thus, right saccade was proved to be associated with spatial attention (see Appendix VII: Hypothesis 2-task 3).

Last, based on the amygdala lateralization models, three hypotheses were raised up. Referring to amygdala lateralization based on emotional valance, the left amygdala activation (positive or negative emotions and contents) will be reflected by a right saccade. Referring to amygdala lateralization based on recall, the left amygdala activation will be reflected by a right saccade. In the contrary to the above, the right amygdala activation during recall will be reflected by a left saccade. The first model of amygdala lateralization in terms of arousal suggest that left amygdala activation will be reflected by a right saccade. A non-parametric chi-square was performed and

results indicate this statement. ($\chi^2(1) = 15.385, p < 0.01$). Results indicate that such activation did not reflect statistically a right saccade ($\chi^2(1) = 0.154, p = 0.695$). Yet, it should be underlined that 23 out of 26 participants reflect a right saccade, while 12 out of 26 expressed arousal. In terms of arousal regarding arousal based on content in model 1, a chi square was also used for examining whether during content-arousal will be reflected by a right saccade. Results indicate that such activation reflects a right saccade ($\chi^2(1) = 12.462, p < 0.01$) (Appendix VIII: Hypothesis 3-model 1).

The second model of amygdala lateralization in terms of recall suggest that left amygdala activation will be reflected by a right saccade. A non-parametric chi-square was performed and results indicate this statement ($\chi^2(2) = 10.692, p < 0.01$). Last, the third model of amygdala lateralization in terms of recall suggests that right amygdala activation will be reflected by a left saccade. A non-parametric chi-square was performed and results indicate this statements ($\chi^2(2) = 10.692, p < 0.01$) (Appendix VIII: Hypothesis 3-model 2). Last, the third model of amygdala lateralization in terms of recall suggests that right amygdala activation will be reflected by a left saccade. A non-parametric chi-square was performed and results indicate this statements ($\chi^2(2) = 10.692, p < 0.01$) (Appendix VIII: Hypothesis 3-model 3).

In this concern, a Multiple Regression was performed in order to evaluate which of the above mentioned variable could predict eye movement. Results indicated that the 88% of the saccade direction can only be predicted by the emotional arousal. $Saccade = 0.961 * \text{expressing arousal via emotion}$ (see Appendix IX: Multiple Regression).

For the purpose of this study 6 women diagnosed with Multiple Sclerosis were also recruited. Frequencies were examined via descriptive statistics in orders the saccade orientation per task and per content and emotional arousal. As far as arousal in terms of emotion and content, 33,3% emotionally aroused in positive content and 50% negative contexts while the rest expressed neutral emotional reaction. All of the MS participants reflect a left saccade and had an arousal in expressing emotions and contents. The 50% expressed negative content and 66.7% expressed negative emotion towards story telling task. As far as narrative memory is concerned, 83.3% reflected a left saccade confirming NLP assumptions. The same results were observed in object

recognition and spatial attention recall tasks. In terms of lesions, the 33.3% had 9 lesions; the 16.7% had 7,12,13,16 appreciatively. As far as lesions in left amygdala are concerned 33.3% had 2 and 4 lesions and 16.7% had 3 and 5 lesions. The 33.3% of MS sample had lesions in prefrontal cortex, while 2,5 and 7 lesions had being observed in the 16.7% . The 50% of our participants had 2 lesions in left hippocampus, while 3,5 and 6 were observed in 16.7% appreciatively (see Appendix X: Multiple Sclerosis Frequencies).

One sample t-test was conducted to determine if a statistical significant difference existed in saccade reflection in narrative memory task, from the number of lesions in amygdala in MS patients. Results indicated that there is a significant difference between those who had a left and those having a right saccade $t(5) = 6.742$, $p < 0.01$. Specifically, all had a left saccade.

One sample t-test was conducted to determine if a statistical significant difference existed in saccade reflection in object recognition memory task, from the number of lesions in left hippocampus in MS patients. Results indicated that there is a significant difference between those who had a left and those having a right saccade $t(5) = 4.663$, $p < 0.01$. Specifically, all had a left saccade.

One sample t-test was conducted to determine if a statistical significant difference existed in saccade reflection in spatial attention task, from the number of lesions in left hippocampus in MS patients. Results indicated that there is a significant difference between those who had a left and those having a right saccade $t(5) = 5.398$, $p < 0.01$. Specifically, all had a left saccade (see Appendix XI: Multiple Sclerosis' Results).

CHAPTER 4

DISCUSSION

In terms of qualitative evaluation, all of the participants reflected negative emotional arousal. Such an outcome, agrees with Cognitive Emotional Therapeutic approach, which interprets automatic thoughts as negative thinking way on establishing behaviour and they are emotionally intercorrelated to core beliefs system (Beck, 1995). Yet, this reflects the first reaction to sudden and unknown concepts. The behavioural reaction changed by the clarification of the next theme that, based on psychodynamic approach, is compromising the personality types, reflects the optimistic type and the coping strategies which underlines that even if the first reaction is related to core beliefs, social influence and individual goals, have an impact in individual's expectations for solution (Prati & Pietrantonio, 2009). Emotional coping strategies could be the answer in such observation, underlining the conflict of an unknown and sudden situation in terms of automatic thinking and by approaching the "fight or flight" state (Leonard & Myint, 2009). This seems to be associated with expectations of the way that a conflict could be resolved, proving the need that individuals have for an instant and successful solution to each conflict. The above implications, underlined the need of synthetic approaches in maladaptive behaviours.

The major aim of this study was to examine the relationship between memory and imagination cognitive tasks in association to eye movements, as referred within NLP theory. By observing frequencies it was proved that 42, 3 % followed the NLP claims concerning left saccade. Such a result, indicates that a vast percent of population have implications of NLP in daily life. Automatic reactions are proving a left saccade once they were recalling a task. Given the fact that a vast majority of the present population underlined CBT indications about automatic thoughts and their negative nature (Beck, 1979; Beck, 1995; Visla et al., 2013;), it could be assumed that in case of first session a therapist could identify the nature of the core belief by the saccade. Yet, more investigation should be done so to generalize this result.

Concerning imagination, right saccade occurred throughout the process of building up a story, by the 73%. This means that in terms of imagination, the left hemisphere is activated meaning that areas such as fusiform gyrus and insula are creating faces and analyzing facial expressions (Howard et al, 1998; Pavuluri & May, 2015; Peelen &

Downing, 2005). The above is determined by the usage of the first picture of TAT, which, as psychodynamic framework imply, triggers imagination and emotional content (Anderson, 1994; Cramer, 2004). This implication could be used in psycho-education and coaching. In such manner, special education practitioners could use this outcome in order to aid children with developmental needs to engage in creative activities. Out of this, this outcome could be applied in interventions referred to rational emotional theory (RET) (Ellis, 1955), by interfering between choice making phase and choice-system by activating emotional arousal and emotional decision making.

Within this research, it was examined whether the right hemispheric activation during memory task is reflected via left saccadic eye movements. Further, it was screened whether left hemispheric activation during imagination task is reflected via right saccadic eye movements (Grindel & Bandler, 1979). Results of the present study claimed a partial support to NLP eye movement model, as even if left eye movements were not significantly associated with memory recall cognitive task, it was proved that there was a significant association between imagination cognitive task and right eye movements. Such results are, to some extent, contradictory to previous research suggesting that there is no significant association between NLP assumptions and eye movements (Cheney et al., 1982; Man et al., 2012; Wiseman et al., 2012). Simultaneously, the above results are linear to a respectful amount of previous research supporting an association between eye movements and cognitive tasks (Buckner et al., 1987; Burke et al., 2003; Ehrlichman et al., 2007; Vrij et al., 2015; Wertheim et al., 1986). This could offer insights regarding the missing points between the NLP effectiveness and the NLP criticism. Specifically, it proves that, NLP is a topic that should be approached as scientifically as the rest topics of neuropsychology and cognitive neuroscience. In an analytic manner, the present implication underlines the need of tasks that apply to certain topography and screenings of cerebrum activation in a combination to computerized programs observing the eye kinaesthetic behaviour. An instant example is the usage of Cohen's logic task (1962), Rey phonological and verbal loop-memory task (1964) and Facial Emotional Expression Screening test (FEST: Ekman 60 and Hexagon) (Ekman & Friesen, 1975) in a combination to saccade tracker.

Yet, examining the potential neuropsychological models underlying on specific eye kinaesthetic behaviour, concerning the lateralization of specific brain regions such as

Prefrontal cortex (Proper et al., 2013; Tulving et al., 1994) and amygdala during memory recall (Bernstein et al., 2002; Sergerie et al., 2005; Yamamoto et al., 2017) or arousal (Canli et al., 2002; Killgore & Yurgelun-Todd, 2001; Sergerie et al., 2008; Schneider et al., 1997; Zald & Pardo, 1997), the present outcomes, are in line with literature supporting a left lateralisation preference of amygdala during emotional arousal (Canli et al., 2002; Killgore & Yurgelun-Todd, 2001; Sergerie et al., 2008; Schneider et al., 1997; Zald & Pardo, 1997). Apparent result was indicated by a significant association between emotional arousal (Positive or negative) and right eye movement. Such findings indicate that, based on a specific lateralization model of amygdala region, eye movements could be further investigated as a non verbal indicator of emotional processing enhancing the therapeutic procedure and further offers new insights for EMDR therapy. Specifically, the implication provided in this result could positively be associated with emotional regulation task of EMDR therapy, as a component proving left hemisphere activation. Analytically, the eye kinaesthetic information could empower the therapeutic alliance via additional emotional aspect reflected by the right saccade (left amygdala activation- arousal).

As far as multiple sclerosis- patients is concerned, results indicated that NLP claims based lesion- topography were confirmed, meaning that left saccades were significantly associated with recalling tasks (narrative memory, object recognition and spatial attention task). On the contrary, right saccades of MS- patients were not associated during the imagination task. While NLP supports that constructing a story reflects a right saccade, ms patients reflect a left saccade. Thus, there is a differential progress between the two included populations in the research. Hence, it should be taken into account there is dislocation of amygdala activation in MS patients clarifying the bilateralization. In such terms, intensity of negative emotions was evaluated by lesions in left amygdala proving that the lateralization of amygdala could change the NLP assumption based on lesions and seizures supporting the model of amygdala which states a right saccade reflects left amygdala activation. This implies that amygdala is activated by the time of construction phase. Such a clarification can easily explained by the cerebrum hierarchy and the fact that brain functionality is not a one to one process. Further research is needed to clarify the role of fusiform gyrus and insula.

Limitations and Future Studies

One of the limitations of our study it was that all of our participants were right handed. Therefore, somehow HERA model and NLP could not be examined. Hence, a future study should include both right handed and left handed participants. Another limitation of this study concerns the video camera; It should have been used a computerized program that by phonological loops could record saccades. Specifically, this program should have the capability to track saccade once an emotional word will be expressed. Accordingly, it is suggested the development of a battery that would examine the perception and recognition of emotions and then would combine verbal and visual recording of saccades and emotions. One more study that should be performed is in concern of gyrus and insula. It seems that the identification of the child's face and specific expression should evaluate again via this localization due to the observed emotional arousal of participants.

To sum up, the most important findings of the present paper refer to the partial support in NLP via the neuropsychological perspective, implying the need for a further research concerning the facial behavioural cues comparing to the cognitive tasks and fMRI evidence-based. In a similar vein, the potential role of amygdala on saccades due to the emotional processing, present the potentiality to be deployed as therapeutic approach which will enable the effectiveness of therapeutic alliance, in cases which the non-verbal behaviour is fundamental for the treatment outcome. Last, this research's findings imply the importance of the neuropsychological principles, underlying EMDR therapy concerning eye-movements, throughout the emotional regulation phase. Even so, further research is necessary for evaluating this implication.

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APPENDICES

Appendix I: Cardiff Committee Ethics Approval

Friday, 03 March 2017

cshs/ethics /approved

Lachanas, Vlassios
BSc (Hons) Psychology
Cardiff School of Health Sciences

Dear Applicant

Re: Application for Ethical Approval: Decoding the Face: The role of Amygdala on Face Behavioural Cues

Project Reference Number : 9007

Your ethics application, as shown above, was considered by the Psychology Ethics Panel on 01/03/2017.

I am pleased to inform you that your application for ethical approval was **APPROVED**.

Minor issues may still need addressing before you commence any work – if so these will be listed below.

- 1. Remove student email and include supervisors email on information sheet.**
- 2. Choose one consent form. There are 2 included.**

Where changes to the information sheet, consent form and/or procedures are deemed necessary you must submit revised versions to the relevant ethics inbox. If you are a student – your supervisor must do this on your behalf.

Note: Failure to comply with any issues listed above will nullify this approval.

Standard Conditions of Approval

1. Your Ethics Application has been given a Project Reference number as above. This **MUST** be quoted on all documentation relating to the project (E.g. consent forms, information sheets), together with the full project title.

2. All documents must also have the approved University Logo and the Version number in addition to the reference and project title as above
3. A full **Risk Assessment** must be undertaken for this proposal, as appropriate, and be made available to the Committee if requested.
4. Any changes in connection to the proposal as approved, must be referred to the Panel/Committee for consideration **without delay quoting your Project Reference Number**. Changes to the proposed project may have ethical implications so must be approved.
5. Any untoward incident which occurs in connection with this proposal must be reported back to the Panel **without delay**.
6. If your project involves the use of **human samples**, your approval is given on the condition that you or your supervisor **notify the HTA Designated Individual** of your intention to work with such material by **completing** the form entitled "*Notification of Intention to Work with Human Samples*". The form must be submitted to the PD (Sean Duggan), **BEFORE** any activity on this project is undertaken

This approval expires on **01/03/2018** . It is your responsibility to reapply / request extension if necessary.

Yours sincerely

**Dr Nick
Perham
Chair
Psychology Research Ethics Committee**

Cardiff School of Health Sciences

Tel : 029 20416255

E-mail : nperham@cardiffmet.ac.uk

PLEASE RETAIN THIS LETTER FOR REFERENCE

Appendix II: Information Sheet and Consent Form

Information Sheet

[The Role of Amygdala on Facial Behavioural Cues]

Dear Participant,

I would like to invite you to participate in this project, which is concerned the facial behavioural cues and their connection to emotional memory. You will be asked to recall a memory based on several images that will be shown to you.

The project is part of my final year for my degree course at the University of Cardiff. It is hoped that the project could provide useful information regarding facial behavioural cues and cognition. Therefore some of it aspect could be included in the doctor-patient communication as well as the therapeutic approach.

Return the response slip to me in the envelope provided so that I know you are interested. Then we will arrange an appointment, which is convenient for you in Polyclinic of Evagelismos or City Unity College.

During the appointment, I will ask information concerning demographic. Then you will look at Snellen table. After that you will complete the Edinburgh Handedness Inventory and you will be provided with a Thematic Analysis Test images asked to build up a story based on them. During the time that you will build up the story you should look at an eye-tracker. This will last for about 30 to 40 minutes and you have the right to withdraw at any time without explaining the reason. When I have completed the study I will produce a summary of the findings which I will be more than happy to send you if you are interested.

If you agree to take part, your name will not be recorded on the questionnaires and the information will not be disclosed to other parties. Your responses to the questions will be used for the purpose of this project only and I will not have access to any of your medical records. You can be assured that if you take part in the project you will remain anonymous.

In case that you are interested in your results you can contact me or my supervisor at the e-mail bellow:

Researcher Name: Vlassios Lachanas

Researcher's email: V.lachanas@cityu.gr

[Supervisor's Name: Maria Zannikou](#)

[Supervisor's e-mail: m.zannikou@cityu.gr](mailto:m.zannikou@cityu.gr)

Cardiff
Metropolitan
University

Prifysgol
Metropolitan
Caerdydd

PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

Participant Reference Number:

Participant name:

Title of Project: The Role of Emotional Memory on Eye Movement

Ethical Approval Number:

Name of Researcher: Vlassios Lachanas

Participant to complete this section: Please initial each box.

1. I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to

withdraw at any time, without giving any reason.

3. I agree to take part in the above study.

Signature of Participant

Date

Name of person taking consent

Date

Signature of person taking consent

** When completed, give 1 copy for participant & 1 copy for researcher site file.*

Appendix III: Example of Qualitative Analysis

Participant 048

Transcript

Question 1	1.	1. Can you tell me a story about the picture that you saw?	
Story telling	1	Ehm so it is a boy which ehm his father wants	Cognitive task Narrative
Father Pressure	2	to make him musician he wants child to learn	Negative content Pressure
Dislike	3	playing the violin but child don't like it. Ehm	Negative Content Dislike
Desire	4	the child wants to draw he likes very much	Positive content Desire
Desire	5	sketching ehm and he shits under the paper and	Positive content Desire
Sad	6	his violin and he is sad. Because he don't wants	Negative emotion Sadness
Pressure	7	to learn playing violin and he is thinking what	Negative content Pressure
Desire	8	he should do because he likes sketching and he	Positive content Desire
Desire	9	wants to follow this career and his father is	
Father Pressure	10	pressing him to learn violin.	Negative content Pressure
Question 2		2. What was the child might thinking or feeling?	
Pressure Sadness	11	Ehm he was feeling pressure ehm and sadness	Negative emotion Sadness/ Negative content Pressure
Dislike	12	Because he don't like at all the violin and he	Negative content Dislike
Trapped	13	feels trapped and that he wants to get away	Negative content Getaway
Getaway	14	from all this because he wants to learn drawing.	
Question 3		3. Do you remember what the child was wearing?	
Recall effort	15	Ehm one white t-shirt? I think.	Recall effort
Question 4		Examiner: Except from the violin and the notebook, what other object there was in the desk?	
Recall effort	16	Ehm except?	Recall effort
EXAMINER REPEAT QUESTION			
Recall effort	17	I didn't observe something else to be honest.	Recall Effort

ORDINATE THEMES	CODES	EVIDENCE	
<u>Negative Emotions</u>	Sadness	6,11	
<u>Negative Content</u>	Pressure	1-2,6-7,10,11	
	Dislike	3	
	Getaway	13-14	
<u>Positive Emotions</u>	-	-	
<u>Positive Content</u>	Desire	4-5,8	
<u>Memory</u>	Recall effort	15,16,17	
<u>Conscious Task</u>			
<u>Eye Movements (Saccades)</u>	Right (Down)	6	
	Right (Middle)	1,7,11,11,11,13,16	
	Right (Up)	1,3	
	Left (Down)	-	
	Left (Middle)	1,1,2,4,5,8,8,9,11,11, 11,15,15,16,16,16,17	
	Left (Up)	1,1,11,14,16	
	Center	1,1,1,3,3,4,5,6,6,9,11, 11,11,11,11,14,15,15 16,16,16,16,17	
	Center (Up)	15	

Interview transcript including eye movement's log

Interviewer: I would like to tell me one story about the photo you saw. (4sec)

Interviewee: RU(4sec) R(4sec) LU(4sec) L(4sec) C(5sec) ehm L(6sec) C(sec) so it is a boy which LU(13sec) C(14sec) ehm his father wants to make him musician L(22sec) he wants child to learn playing the violin but child don't C(24sec) like it. RU(27sec) ehm C(28sec) the child wants L(32sec) to draw C(32sec) he likes very much sketching L(35sec) ehm and he shits under C(38sec) the paper and his violin RD(44sec) and he is sad C(44sec). Because he L(46sec) C(46sec) don't wants R(47sec) don't want to learn playing violin and he is thinking L(51sec) what he should do because he likes sketching and he wants to follow this career L(56sec) C(56sec) and his father is oppressing him to learn violin.

Interviewer: What was the child might thinking or feeling? (00:01:02)

Interviewee: L(00:01:03) C(00:01:04) ehm LU(00:01:06) C(00:01:07) L(00:01:07) C(00:01:08) R(00:01:09) C(00:01:10) he was feeling pressure R(00:01:13) ehm L(00:01:14) C(00:01:14) and R(00:01:15) sadness C(00:01:16) because he don't like at all the violin and he feels R(00:01:22) trapped and that he wants to get away C(00:01:23) from all this because he wants to LU(00:01:25) C(00:01:25) learn drawing.

Interviewer: Do you remember what was the child wearing? (00:01:29)

Interviewee: L(00:01:31) CU(00:01:32) ehm C(00:01:33) one white t-shirt L(00:01:34)? I think C(00:01:35)

Interviewer: Except from the notebook and the violin, what other object there was in the desk? (00:01:31)

Interviewee: L(00:01:42) C(00:01:43) L(00:01:43) C(00:01:43) L(00:01:43) R (00:01:46) C(00:01:46) ehm LU(00:01:47) C(00:01:48) except? EXAMINER REPEAT QUESTION (00:01:53) L (00:01:53) i didn't C(00:01:55) observe something else to be honest.

Appendix IV: Test of Normality

Case Processing Summary

	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Sex	11	42,3%	15	57,7%	26	100,0%
Total number of expressed positive content	11	42,3%	15	57,7%	26	100,0%
Total number of expressed negative content	11	42,3%	15	57,7%	26	100,0%
Positive or Negative content-amygdala arousal	11	42,3%	15	57,7%	26	100,0%
Eye Movement Direction Before Narrative	11	42,3%	15	57,7%	26	100,0%
Stimuli Content	11	42,3%	15	57,7%	26	100,0%
Emotions	11	42,3%	15	57,7%	26	100,0%
Emotional thoughts direct Recall amygdala	11	42,3%	15	57,7%	26	100,0%
NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade	11	42,3%	15	57,7%	26	100,0%
NLP Assumption Recall-Left saccade	11	42,3%	15	57,7%	26	100,0%
Object recognition direct recall hippocampus	11	42,3%	15	57,7%	26	100,0%
Object location direct recall PFC	11	42,3%	15	57,7%	26	100,0%
NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade	11	42,3%	15	57,7%	26	100,0%

Existing cues	11	42,3%	15	57,7%	26	100,0%
Eye movement for emotions	11	42,3%	15	57,7%	26	100,0%
Eye movement content	11	42,3%	15	57,7%	26	100,0%
NLP Assumption Construct- Right Saccade	11	42,3%	15	57,7%	26	100,0%
Amygdala Emot Model 1 Assumption Left Arousal(POS/NEG)-Right Saccade	11	42,3%	15	57,7%	26	100,0%
Amygdala Cont Model 1 Assumption Left Arousal(POS/NEG)-Right Saccade	11	42,3%	15	57,7%	26	100,0%
Amygdala Q1 Model 1 Assumption Left Activation Recall-Right Saccade	11	42,3%	15	57,7%	26	100,0%
Amygdala Q1 Model 1 Assumption Right Activation Recall-Left Saccade	11	42,3%	15	57,7%	26	100,0%

Descriptives^a

		Statistic	Std. Error	
Sex	Mean	1,64	,152	
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	1,30	
		Upper Bound	1,98	
	5% Trimmed Mean	1,65		
	Median	2,00		
	Variance	,255		
	Std. Deviation	,505		
	Minimum	1		
	Maximum	2		
	Range	1		
	Interquartile Range	1		
	Skewness	-,661	,661	
	Kurtosis	-1,964	1,279	
	Total number of expressed positive content	Mean	,73	,273
95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Lower Bound	,12	
		Upper Bound	1,33	
5% Trimmed Mean		,64		
Median		1,00		
Variance		,818		
Std. Deviation		,905		
Minimum		0		
Maximum		3		
Range		3		

	Interquartile Range		1	
	Skewness		1,638	,661
	Kurtosis		3,531	1,279
Total number of expressed negative content	Mean		3,27	,541
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	2,07	
		Upper Bound	4,48	
	5% Trimmed Mean		3,25	
	Median		3,00	
	Variance		3,218	
	Std. Deviation		1,794	
	Minimum		1	
	Maximum		6	
	Range		5	
	Interquartile Range		3	
	Skewness		,136	,661
	Kurtosis		-1,626	1,279
	Eye Movement Direction Before Narrative	Mean		1,27
95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Lower Bound	,96	
		Upper Bound	1,59	
5% Trimmed Mean			1,25	
Median			1,00	
Variance			,218	
Std. Deviation			,467	
Minimum			1	
Maximum			2	

	Range		1	
	Interquartile Range		1	
	Skewness		1,189	,661
	Kurtosis		-,764	1,279
Stimuli Content	Mean		1,36	,338
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	,61	
		Upper Bound	2,12	
	5% Trimmed Mean		1,35	
	Median		1,00	
	Variance		1,255	
	Std. Deviation		1,120	
	Minimum		0	
	Maximum		3	
	Range		3	
	Interquartile Range		2	
	Skewness		,155	,661
	Kurtosis		-1,225	1,279
	Emotions	Mean		1,91
95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Lower Bound	1,55	
		Upper Bound	2,27	
5% Trimmed Mean			1,90	
Median			2,00	
Variance			,291	
Std. Deviation			,539	
Minimum			1	

	Maximum		3	
	Range		2	
	Interquartile Range		0	
	Skewness		-,155	,661
	Kurtosis		1,862	1,279
Emotional thoughts direct Recall amygdala	Mean		1,82	,182
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	1,41	
		Upper Bound	2,22	
	5% Trimmed Mean		1,80	
	Median		2,00	
	Variance		,364	
	Std. Deviation		,603	
	Minimum		1	
	Maximum		3	
	Range		2	
	Interquartile Range		1	
	Skewness		,028	,661
	Kurtosis		,412	1,279
	NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade	Mean		,64
95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Lower Bound	,30	
		Upper Bound	,98	
5% Trimmed Mean			,65	
Median			1,00	
Variance			,255	
Std. Deviation			,505	

	Minimum		0	
	Maximum		1	
	Range		1	
	Interquartile Range		1	
	Skewness		-.661	,661
	Kurtosis		-1,964	1,279
NLP Assumption Recall-Left saccade	Mean		,45	,157
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	,10	
		Upper Bound	,81	
	5% Trimmed Mean		,45	
	Median		,00	
	Variance		,273	
	Std. Deviation		,522	
	Minimum		0	
	Maximum		1	
	Range		1	
	Interquartile Range		1	
	Skewness		,213	,661
	Kurtosis		-2,444	1,279
	Object recognition direct recall hippocampus	Mean		1,64
95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Lower Bound	1,18	
		Upper Bound	2,09	
5% Trimmed Mean			1,60	
Median			2,00	
Variance			,455	

	Std. Deviation		,674	
	Minimum		1	
	Maximum		3	
	Range		2	
	Interquartile Range		1	
	Skewness		,593	,661
	Kurtosis		-,293	1,279
Object location direct recall PFC	Mean		1,64	,203
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	1,18	
		Upper Bound	2,09	
	5% Trimmed Mean		1,60	
	Median		2,00	
	Variance		,455	
	Std. Deviation		,674	
	Minimum		1	
	Maximum		3	
	Range		2	
	Interquartile Range		1	
	Skewness		,593	,661
	Kurtosis		-,293	1,279
NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade	Mean		,45	,157
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	,10	
		Upper Bound	,81	
	5% Trimmed Mean		,45	
	Median		,00	

	Variance		,273	
	Std. Deviation		,522	
	Minimum		0	
	Maximum		1	
	Range		1	
	Interquartile Range		1	
	Skewness		,213	,661
	Kurtosis		-2,444	1,279
Existing cues	Mean		1,45	,157
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	1,10	
		Upper Bound	1,81	
	5% Trimmed Mean		1,45	
	Median		1,00	
	Variance		,273	
	Std. Deviation		,522	
	Minimum		1	
	Maximum		2	
	Range		1	
	Interquartile Range		1	
	Skewness		,213	,661
	Kurtosis		-2,444	1,279
Eye movement for emotions	Mean		4,36	,509
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	3,23	
		Upper Bound	5,50	
	5% Trimmed Mean		4,29	

	Median		4,00	
	Variance		2,855	
	Std. Deviation		1,690	
	Minimum		2	
	Maximum		8	
	Range		6	
	Interquartile Range		0	
	Skewness		1,275	,661
	Kurtosis		1,637	1,279
Eye movement content	Mean		3,45	,928
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	1,39	
		Upper Bound	5,52	
	5% Trimmed Mean		3,28	
	Median		4,00	
	Variance		9,473	
	Std. Deviation		3,078	
	Minimum		0	
	Maximum		10	
	Range		10	
	Interquartile Range		4	
	Skewness		,833	,661
	Kurtosis		,789	1,279
NLP Assumption Construct- Right Saccade	Mean		,73	,141
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	,41	
		Upper Bound	1,04	

	5% Trimmed Mean		,75	
	Median		1,00	
	Variance		,218	
	Std. Deviation		,467	
	Minimum		0	
	Maximum		1	
	Range		1	
	Interquartile Range		1	
	Skewness		-1,189	,661
	Kurtosis		-,764	1,279
Amygdala Emot Model 1	Mean		,73	,141
Assumption Left	95% Confidence Interval for	Lower Bound	,41	
Arousal(POS/NEG)-Right	Mean	Upper Bound	1,04	
Saccade	5% Trimmed Mean		,75	
	Median		1,00	
	Variance		,218	
	Std. Deviation		,467	
	Minimum		0	
	Maximum		1	
	Range		1	
	Interquartile Range		1	
	Skewness		-1,189	,661
	Kurtosis		-,764	1,279
Amygdala Cont Model 1	Mean		,45	,157
Assumption Left	95% Confidence Interval for	Lower Bound	,10	
Arousal(POS/NEG)-Right				

Saccade	Mean	Upper Bound	,81		
	5% Trimmed Mean		,45		
	Median		,00		
	Variance		,273		
	Std. Deviation		,522		
	Minimum		0		
	Maximum		1		
	Range		1		
	Interquartile Range		1		
	Skewness		,213	,661	
	Kurtosis		-2,444	1,279	
	Amygdala Q1 Model 1	Mean		,27	,141
	Assumption Left Activation Recall-Right Saccade	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	-,04	
		Upper Bound	,59		
5% Trimmed Mean			,25		
Median			,00		
Variance			,218		
Std. Deviation			,467		
Minimum			0		
Maximum			1		
Range			1		
Interquartile Range			1		
Skewness			1,189	,661	
Kurtosis			-,764	1,279	
Amygdala Q1 Model 1		Mean		,64	,152

Assumption Right Activation Recall-Left Saccade	95% Confidence Interval for	Lower Bound	,30	
	Mean	Upper Bound	,98	
5% Trimmed Mean			,65	
Median			1,00	
Variance			,255	
Std. Deviation			,505	
Minimum			0	
Maximum			1	
Range			1	
Interquartile Range			1	
Skewness			-,661	,661
Kurtosis			-1,964	1,279

a. Positive or Negative content-amygdala arousal is constant. It has been omitted.

Tests of Normality^b

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Sex	,401	11	,000	,625	11	,000
Total number of expressed positive content	,291	11	,010	,734	11	,001
Total number of expressed negative content	,216	11	,162	,897	11	,171
Eye Movement Direction Before Narrative	,448	11	,000	,572	11	,000
Stimuli Content	,173	11	,200*	,889	11	,135
Emotions	,385	11	,000	,724	11	,001
Emotional thoughts direct Recall amygdala	,346	11	,001	,774	11	,004
NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade	,401	11	,000	,625	11	,000
NLP Assumption Recall-Left saccade	,353	11	,000	,649	11	,000
Object recognition direct recall hippocampus	,282	11	,015	,786	11	,006
Object location direct recall PFC	,282	11	,015	,786	11	,006
NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade	,353	11	,000	,649	11	,000
Existing cues	,353	11	,000	,649	11	,000
Eye movement for emotions	,403	11	,000	,769	11	,004
Eye movement content	,248	11	,058	,890	11	,138
NLP Assumption Construct-Right Saccade	,448	11	,000	,572	11	,000

Amygdala Emot Model 1 Assumption Left Arousal(POS/NEG)-Right Saccade	,448	11	,000	,572	11	,000
Amygdala Cont Model 1 Assumption Left Arousal(POS/NEG)-Right Saccade	,353	11	,000	,649	11	,000
Amygdala Q1 Model 1 Assumption Left Activation Recall-Right Saccade	,448	11	,000	,572	11	,000
Amygdala Q1 Model 1 Assumption Right Activation Recall-Left Saccade	,401	11	,000	,625	11	,000

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

b. Positive or Negative content-amygdala arousal is constant. It has been omitted.

Sex

Sex Stem-and-Leaf Plot

Frequency Stem & Leaf

4.00 1 . 0000

.00 1 .

.00 1 .

.00 1 .

.00 1 .

7.00 2 . 0000000

Stem width: 1

Each leaf: 1 case(s)

Normal Q-Q Plot of Sex

Total number of expressed positive content

Total number of expressed positive content Stem-and-Leaf Plot

Frequency Stem & Leaf

5.00 0 . 00000

.00 0 .

.00 0 .

.00 0 .

.00 0 .

5.00 1 . 00000

1.00 Extremes (>=3.0)

Stem width: 1

Each leaf: 1 case(s)

Normal Q-Q Plot of Total number of expressed positive content

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot of Total number of expressed positive content

Total number of expressed negative content

Total number of expressed negative content Stem-and-Leaf Plot

Frequency Stem & Leaf

2.00 1 . 00

3.00 2 . 000

1.00 3 . 0

1.00 4 . 0

3.00 5 . 000

1.00 6 . 0

Stem width: 1

Each leaf: 1 case(s)

Normal Q-Q Plot of Total number of expressed negative content

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot of Total number of expressed negative content

Positive or Negative content-amygdala arousal

Eye Movement Direction Before Narrative

Eye Movement Direction Before Narrative Stem-and-Leaf Plot

Frequency Stem & Leaf

8.00 1 . 00000000

.00 1 .

.00 1 .

.00 1 .

.00 1 .

3.00 2 . 000

Stem width: 1

Each leaf: 1 case(s)

Normal Q-Q Plot of Eye Movement Direction Before Narrative

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot of Eye Movement Direction Before Narrative

Stimuli Content

Stimuli Content Stem-and-Leaf Plot

Frequency Stem & Leaf

3.00 0 . 000

.00 0 .

3.00 1 . 000

.00 1 .

3.00 2 . 000

.00 2 .

2.00 3 . 00

Stem width: 1

Each leaf: 1 case(s)

Normal Q-Q Plot of Stimuli Content

Emotions

Emotions Stem-and-Leaf Plot

Frequency Stem & Leaf

2.00 Extremes (≤ 1)

.00 0 .

8.00 0 . 22222222

1.00 Extremes (≥ 3)

Stem width: 10

Each leaf: 1 case(s)

Normal Q-Q Plot of Emotions

Emotional thoughts direct Recall amygdala

Emotional thoughts direct Recall amygdala Stem-and-Leaf Plot

Frequency Stem & Leaf

3.00 1 . 000

.00 1 .

.00 1 .

.00 1 .

.00 1 .

7.00 2 . 0000000

1.00 Extremes (>=3.0)

Stem width: 1

Each leaf: 1 case(s)

Normal Q-Q Plot of Emotional thoughts direct Recall amygdala

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot of Emotional thoughts direct Recall amygdala

NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade

NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade Stem-and-Leaf Plot

Frequency Stem & Leaf

4.00 0 . 0000

.00 0 .

.00 0 .

.00 0 .

.00 0 .

7.00 1 . 0000000

Stem width: 1

Each leaf: 1 case(s)

Normal Q-Q Plot of NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot of NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade

NLP Assumption Recall-Left saccade

NLP Assumption Recall-Left saccade Stem-and-Leaf Plot

Frequency Stem & Leaf

6.00 0 . 000000

.00 0 .

.00 0 .

.00 0 .

.00 0 .

5.00 1 . 00000

Stem width: 1

Each leaf: 1 case(s)

Normal Q-Q Plot of NLP Assumption Recall-Left saccade

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot of NLP Assumption Recall-Left saccade

Object recognition direct recall hippocampus

Object recognition direct recall hippocampus Stem-and-Leaf Plot

Frequency Stem & Leaf

5.00 1 . 00000

.00 1 .

5.00 2 . 00000

.00 2 .

1.00 3 . 0

Stem width: 1

Each leaf: 1 case(s)

Normal Q-Q Plot of Object recognition direct recall hippocampus

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot of Object recognition direct recall hippocampus

Object location direct recall PFC

Object location direct recall PFC Stem-and-Leaf Plot

Frequency Stem & Leaf

5.00 1 . 00000

.00 1 .

5.00 2 . 00000

.00 2 .

1.00 3 . 0

Stem width: 1

Each leaf: 1 case(s)

Normal Q-Q Plot of Object location direct recall PFC

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot of Object location direct recall PFC

NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade

NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade Stem-and-Leaf Plot

Frequency Stem & Leaf

6.00 0 . 000000

.00 0 .

.00 0 .

.00 0 .

.00 0 .

5.00 1 . 00000

Stem width: 1

Each leaf: 1 case(s)

Normal Q-Q Plot of NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot of NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade

Existing cues

Existing cues Stem-and-Leaf Plot

Frequency Stem & Leaf

6.00 1 . 000000

.00 1 .

.00 1 .

.00 1 .

.00 1 .

5.00 2 . 00000

Stem width: 1

Each leaf: 1 case(s)

Eye movement for emotions

Eye movement for emotions Stem-and-Leaf Plot

Frequency Stem & Leaf

2.00 Extremes (≤ 3)

.00 0 .

7.00 0 . 4444444

2.00 Extremes (≥ 7)

Stem width: 10

Each leaf: 1 case(s)

Eye movement content

Eye movement content Stem-and-Leaf Plot

Frequency Stem & Leaf

3.00 0 . 000

.00 1 .

1.00 2 . 0

1.00 3 . 0

4.00 4 . 0000

.00 5 .

.00 6 .

1.00 7 . 0

1.00 Extremes (≥ 10.0)

Stem width: 1

Each leaf: 1 case(s)

Normal Q-Q Plot of Eye movement content

NLP Assumption Construct-Right Saccade

NLP Assumption Construct-Right Saccade Stem-and-Leaf Plot

Frequency Stem & Leaf

3.00	0 . 000
.00	0 .
.00	0 .
.00	0 .
.00	0 .
8.00	1 . 00000000

Stem width: 1

Each leaf: 1 case(s)

Normal Q-Q Plot of NLP Assumption Construct-Right Saccade

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot of NLP Assumption Construct-Right Saccade

Amygdala Emot Model 1 Assumption Left Arousal(POS/NEG)-Right Saccade

Amygdala Emot Model 1 Assumption Left Arousal(POS/NEG)-Right Saccade Stem-and-Leaf Plot

Frequency Stem & Leaf

3.00 0 . 000

.00 0 .

.00 0 .

.00 0 .

.00 0 .

8.00 1 . 00000000

Stem width: 1

Each leaf: 1 case(s)

Normal Q-Q Plot of Amygdala Emot Model 1 Assumption Left Arousal(POS/NEG)-
Right Saccade

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot of Amygdala Emot Model 1 Assumption Left Arousal (POS/NEG)-Right Saccade

Amygdala Cont Model 1 Assumption Left Arousal(POS/NEG)-Right Saccade

Amygdala Cont Model 1 Assumption Left Arousal(POS/NEG)-Right Saccade Stem-and-Leaf Plot

Frequency Stem & Leaf

6.00 0 . 000000

.00 0 .

.00 0 .

.00 0 .

.00 0 .

5.00 1 . 00000

Stem width: 1

Each leaf: 1 case(s)

Normal Q-Q Plot of Amygdala Cont Model 1 Assumption Left Arousal(POS/NEG)-
Right Saccade

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot of Amygdala Cont Model 1 Assumption Left Arousal (POS/NEG)-Right Saccade

Amygdala Q1 Model 1 Assumption Left Activation Recall-Right Saccade

Amygdala Q1 Model 1 Assumption Left Activation Recall-Right Saccade Stem-and-Leaf Plot

Frequency Stem & Leaf

8.00 0 . 00000000

.00 0 .

.00 0 .

.00 0 .

.00 0 .

3.00 1 . 000

Stem width: 1

Each leaf: 1 case(s)

Normal Q-Q Plot of Amygdala Q1 Model 1 Assumption Left Activation Recall-Right Saccade

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot of Amygdala Q1 Model 1 Assumption Left Activation Recall-Right Saccade

Amygdala Q1 Model 1 Assumption Right Activation Recall-Left Saccade

Amygdala Q1 Model 1 Assumption Right Activation Recall-Left Saccade Stem-and-Leaf Plot

Frequency Stem & Leaf

4.00 0 . 0000

.00 0 .

.00 0 .

.00 0 .

.00 0 .

7.00 1 . 0000000

Stem width: 1

Each leaf: 1 case(s)

Normal Q-Q Plot of Amygdala Q1 Model 1 Assumption Right Activation Recall-Left Saccade

Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot of Amygdala Q1 Model 1 Assumption Right Activation Recall-Left Saccade

Appendix V: Frequencies for Healthy Population

	Sex	Total number of expressed positive content	Total number of expressed negative content	Positive or Negative content-amygdala arousal	Eye Movement Direction Before Narrative
N Valid	26	26	26	26	26
Missing	0	0	0	0	0

	Stimuli Content	Emotions	Emotional thoughts direct Recall amygdala	NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade	NLP Assumption Recall-Left saccade
N Valid	26	26	26	26	26
Missing	0	0	0	0	0

	Object recognition direct recall hippocampus	Object location direct recall PFC	NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade	Eye movement for emotions	Eye movement content
N Valid	26	26	26	26	26
Missing	0	0	0	0	0

Statistics

	NLP Assumption Construct-Right Saccade	Amygdala Emot Model 1 Assumption Left Arousal(POS/NEG)-Right Saccade	Amygdala Cont Model 1 Assumption Left Arousal(POS/NEG)-Right Saccade	Amygdala Q1 Model 1 Assumption Left Activation Recall-Right Saccade	Amygdala Q1 Model 1 Assumption Right Activation Recall-Left Saccade
N Valid	26	11	26	26	26
Missing	0	15	0	0	0

Frequency Table

Sex

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	13	50,0	50,0	50,0
	female	13	50,0	50,0	100,0
	Total	26	100,0	100,0	

Total number of expressed positive content

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	0	9	34,6	34,6	34,6
	1	12	46,2	46,2	80,8
	2	1	3,8	3,8	84,6
	3	3	11,5	11,5	96,2
	4	1	3,8	3,8	100,0
	Total	26	100,0	100,0	

Total number of expressed negative content

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	0	4	15,4	15,4	15,4
	1	5	19,2	19,2	34,6
	2	5	19,2	19,2	53,8
	3	5	19,2	19,2	73,1
	4	2	7,7	7,7	80,8
	5	4	15,4	15,4	96,2
	6	1	3,8	3,8	100,0
	Total	26	100,0	100,0	

Positive or Negative content-amygdala arousal

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Non Arousal	1	3,8	3,8	3,8
	Arousal	25	96,2	96,2	100,0
	Total	26	100,0	100,0	

Eye Movement Direction Before Narrative

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Right	19	73,1	73,1	73,1
	Left	6	23,1	23,1	96,2
	Center	1	3,8	3,8	100,0
	Total	26	100,0	100,0	

Stimuli Content

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	neutral	4	15,4	15,4	15,4
	Positive	6	23,1	23,1	38,5
	Negative	6	23,1	23,1	61,5
	Both Negative and Positive Content	10	38,5	38,5	100,0
	Total	26	100,0	100,0	

Emotions

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	neutral	14	53,8	53,8	53,8
	Positive	2	7,7	7,7	61,5
	Negative	9	34,6	34,6	96,2
	Both Negative and Positive Emotion	1	3,8	3,8	100,0
	Total	26	100,0	100,0	

Emotional thoughts direct Recall amygdala

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Right	14	53,8	53,8	53,8
	Left	11	42,3	42,3	96,2
	Center	1	3,8	3,8	100,0
	Total	26	100,0	100,0	

NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Non Associative- R or C	15	57,7	57,7	57,7
	Associative- L	11	42,3	42,3	100,0
	Total	26	100,0	100,0	

NLP Assumption Recall-Left saccade

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Non Associative- R or C	17	65,4	65,4	65,4
	Associative- L	9	34,6	34,6	100,0
	Total	26	100,0	100,0	

Object recognition direct recall hippocampus

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Right	13	50,0	50,0	50,0
	Left	9	34,6	34,6	84,6
	Center	4	15,4	15,4	100,0
	Total	26	100,0	100,0	

Object location direct recall PFC

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Right	15	57,7	57,7	57,7
	Left	10	38,5	38,5	96,2
	Center	1	3,8	3,8	100,0
	Total	26	100,0	100,0	

NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Non Associative- R or C	16	61,5	61,5	61,5
	Associative- L	10	38,5	38,5	100,0
	Total	26	100,0	100,0	

Eye movement for emotions

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Center-Neutral	14	53,8	53,8	53,8
Center-Negative	1	3,8	3,8	57,7
Right-Positive	1	3,8	3,8	61,5
Right-Negative	7	26,9	26,9	88,5
Left-Positive	1	3,8	3,8	92,3
Left-Negative	1	3,8	3,8	96,2
Both Right and Left-Negative	1	3,8	3,8	100,0
Total	26	100,0	100,0	

Eye movement content

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Center-Neutral	4	15,4	15,4	15,4
Center-Positive	2	7,7	7,7	23,1
Center-Negative	1	3,8	3,8	26,9
Right-Positive	1	3,8	3,8	30,8
Right-Negative	12	46,2	46,2	76,9
Left-Positive	4	15,4	15,4	92,3
Left-Negative	1	3,8	3,8	96,2
Both Right and Left-Positive	1	3,8	3,8	100,0
Total	26	100,0	100,0	

NLP Assumption Construct-Right Saccade

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Non Associative- L or C	7	26,9	26,9	26,9
	Associative- R	19	73,1	73,1	100,0
	Total	26	100,0	100,0	

Appendix VI: Hypothesis 1

NPar Tests

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Eye Movement Direction Before Narrative	26	1,31	,549	1	3
NLP Assumption Construct-Right Saccade	26	,73	,452	0	1

Chi-Square Test

Frequencies

Eye Movement Direction Before Narrative

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Right	19	8,7	10,3
Left	6	8,7	-2,7
Center	1	8,7	-7,7
Total	26		

NLP Assumption Construct-Right Saccade

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Non Associative- L or C	7	13,0	-6,0
Associative- R	19	13,0	6,0
Total	26		

Test Statistics

	Eye Movement Direction Before Narrative	NLP Assumption Construct-Right Saccade
Chi-Square	19,923 ^a	5,538 ^b
df	2	1
Asymp. Sig.	,000	,019

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 8.7.

b. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 13.0.

Appendix VI: Hypothesis 1- Extended Hypothesis a

NPar Tests

Mann-Whitney Test

Ranks

	expressing arousal emotion	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Total number of expressed positive content	non exp emotion	14	14,32	200,50
	expressing emotion	12	12,54	150,50
	Total	26		
Total number of expressed negative content	non exp emotion	14	10,71	150,00
	expressing emotion	12	16,75	201,00
	Total	26		

Test Statistics^a

	Total number of expressed positive content	Total number of expressed negative content
Mann-Whitney U	72,500	45,000
Wilcoxon W	150,500	150,000
Z	-,638	-2,034
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	,524	,042
Exact Sig. [2*(1-tailed Sig.)]	,560 ^b	,046 ^b

a. Grouping Variable: expressing arousal emotion

b. Not corrected for ties.

Appendix VI: Hypothesis 1- Extended Hypothesis b

Kruskal-Wallis Test

Ranks			
	Eye movement content	N	Mean Rank
Total number of expressed positive content	Center-Positive	2	19,00
	Center-Negative	1	3,50
	Right-Positive	1	12,00
	Right-Negative	12	10,67
	Left-Positive	4	14,00
	Left-Negative	1	3,50
	Both Right and Left-Positive	1	12,00
	Total	22	
Total number of expressed negative content	Center-Positive	2	8,50
	Center-Negative	1	10,00
	Right-Positive	1	5,50
	Right-Negative	12	14,29
	Left-Positive	4	7,25
	Left-Negative	1	10,00
	Both Right and Left-Positive	1	10,00
	Total	22	

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	Total number of expressed positive content	Total number of expressed negative content
Chi-Square	7,620	5,554
df	6	6
Asymp. Sig.	,027	,047

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: Eye movement content

Appendix VII: Hypothesis 2- Task 1

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Emotional thoughts direct Recall amygdala	26	1,50	,583	1	3
NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade	26	,42	,504	0	1

Chi-Square Test

Frequencies

Emotional thoughts direct Recall amygdala

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Right	14	8,7	5,3
Left	11	8,7	2,3
Center	1	8,7	-7,7
Total	26		

NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Non Associative- R or C	15	13,0	2,0
Associative- L	11	13,0	-2,0
Total	26		

Test Statistics

	Emotional thoughts direct Recall amygdala	NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade
Chi-Square	10,692 ^a	,615 ^b
df	2	1
Asymp. Sig.	,005	,433

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 8.7.

b. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 13.0.

Appendix VII: Hypothesis 2- Task 2

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Object recognition direct recall hippocampus	26	1,65	,745	1	3
NLP Assumption Recall-Left saccade	26	,35	,485	0	1

Chi-Square Test

Frequencies

Object recognition direct recall hippocampus

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Right	13	8,7	4,3
Left	9	8,7	,3
Center	4	8,7	-4,7
Total	26		

NLP Assumption Recall-Left saccade

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Non Associative- R or C	17	13,0	4,0
Associative- L	9	13,0	-4,0
Total	26		

Test Statistics

	Object recognition direct recall hippocampus	NLP Assumption Recall-Left saccade
Chi-Square	4,692 ^a	2,462 ^b
df	2	1
Asymp. Sig.	,096	,117

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 8.7.

b. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 13.0.

Appendix VII: Hypothesis 2- Task 3

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Object location direct recall PFC	26	1,46	,582	1	3
NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade	26	,38	,496	0	1

Chi-Square Test

Frequencies

Object location direct recall PFC

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Right	15	8,7	6,3
Left	10	8,7	1,3
Center	1	8,7	-7,7
Total	26		

NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Non Associative- R or C	16	13,0	3,0
Associative- L	10	13,0	-3,0
Total	26		

Test Statistics

	Object location direct recall PFC	NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade
Chi-Square	11,615 ^a	1,385 ^b
df	2	1
Asymp. Sig.	,003	,239

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 8.7.

b. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 13.0.

Appendix VIII: Hypothesis 3- Model 1

Chi-Square Test

Frequencies

Amygdala Emot Model 1 Assumption Left Arousal(POS/NEG)-Right Saccade

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Non Associative- L or C	3	13,0	-10,0
Associative- R	23	13,0	10,0
Total	26		

expressing arousal content

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
non exp emotion	4	13,0	-9,0
expressing emotion	22	13,0	9,0
Total	26		

Test Statistics

	Amygdala Emot Model 1 Assumption Left Arousal(POS/N EG)-Right Saccade	expressing arousal content
Chi-Square	15,385 ^a	12,462 ^a
df	1	1
Asymp. Sig.	,000	,000

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 13.0.

Chi-Square Test

Frequencies

Amygdala Emot Model 1 Assumption Left Arousal(POS/NEG)-Right Saccade

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Non Associative- L or C	3	13,0	-10,0
Associative- R	23	13,0	10,0
Total	26		

expressing arousal emotion

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
non exp emotion	14	13,0	1,0
expressing emotion	12	13,0	-1,0
Total	26		

Test Statistics

	Amygdala Emot Model 1 Assumption Left Arousal(POS/N EG)-Right Saccade	expressing arousal emotion
Chi-Square	15,385 ^a	,154 ^a
df	1	1
Asymp. Sig.	,000	,695

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 13.0.

Appendix VIII: Hypothesis 3- Model 2

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Amygdala Q1 Model 2 Assumption Left Activation Recall-Right Saccade	26	,54	,508	0	1
Emotional thoughts direct Recall amygdala	26	1,50	,583	1	3

Chi-Square Test

Frequencies

Amygdala Q1 Model 2 Assumption Left Activation Recall-Right Saccade

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Non Associative- L or C	12	13,0	-1,0
Associative- R	14	13,0	1,0
Total	26		

Emotional thoughts direct Recall amygdala

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Right	14	8,7	5,3
Left	11	8,7	2,3
Center	1	8,7	-7,7
Total	26		

Test Statistics

	Amygdala Q1 Model 2 Assumption Left Activation Recall-Right Saccade	Emotional thoughts direct Recall amygdala
Chi-Square	,154 ^a	10,692 ^b
df	1	2
Asymp. Sig.	,695	,005

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 13.0.

b. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 8.7.

Appendix VIII: Hypothesis 3- Model 3

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Emotional thoughts direct Recall amygdala	26	1,50	,583	1	3
Amygdala Q1 Model 3 Assumption Right Activation Recall-Left Saccade	26	,42	,504	0	1

Chi-Square Test

Frequencies

Emotional thoughts direct Recall amygdala

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Right	14	8,7	5,3
Left	11	8,7	2,3
Center	1	8,7	-7,7
Total	26		

Amygdala Q1 Model 3 Assumption Right Activation Recall-Left

Saccade

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Non Associative- R or C	15	13,0	2,0
Associative- L	11	13,0	-2,0
Total	26		

Test Statistics

	Emotional thoughts direct Recall amygdala	Amygdala Q1 Model 3 Assumption Right Activation Recall-Left Saccade
Chi-Square	10,692 ^a	,615 ^b
df	2	1
Asymp. Sig.	,005	,433

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 8.7.

b. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 13.0.

Appendix IX: Multiple- Regression

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	expressing arousal content, Amygdala Q1 Model 2 Assumption Left Activation Recall-Right Saccade, Amygdala Cont Model 1 Assumption Left Arousal(POS/N EG)-Right Saccade, expressing arousal emotion, Amygdala Q1 Model 3 Assumption Right Activation Recall-Left Saccade ^b		Enter

a. Dependent Variable: Eye movement for emotions

b. Tolerance = .000 limit reached.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,880 ^a	,775	,719	1,478

a. Predictors: (Constant), expressing arousal content, Amygdala Q1 Model 2 Assumption Left Activation Recall-Right Saccade, Amygdala Cont Model 1 Assumption Left Arousal(POS/NEG)-Right Saccade, expressing arousal emotion, Amygdala Q1 Model 3 Assumption Right Activation Recall-Left Saccade

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	150,376	5	30,075	13,776	,000 ^b
	Residual	43,663	20	2,183		
	Total	194,038	25			

a. Dependent Variable: Eye movement for emotions

b. Predictors: (Constant), expressing arousal content, Amygdala Q1 Model 2 Assumption Left Activation Recall-Right Saccade, Amygdala Cont Model 1 Assumption Left Arousal(POS/NEG)-Right Saccade, expressing arousal emotion, Amygdala Q1 Model 3 Assumption Right Activation Recall-Left Saccade

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t		
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	-1,883	1,952		-,965	
	Amygdala Cont Model 1 Assumption Left Arousal(POS/NEG)-Right Saccade	-,541	,710	-,099	-,762	
	Amygdala Q1 Model 2 Assumption Left Activation Recall-Right Saccade	1,252	1,653	,228	,757	
	Amygdala Q1 Model 3 Assumption Right Activation Recall-Left Saccade	,617	1,623	,112	,380	
	expressing arousal emotion	5,265	,729	,961	7,224	
	expressing arousal content	1,159	,940	,153	1,233	

Coefficients^a

Model		Sig.
1	(Constant)	,346
	Amygdala Cont Model 1 Assumption Left Arousal(POS/NEG)- Right Saccade	,455
	Amygdala Q1 Model 2 Assumption Left Activation Recall-Right Saccade	,458
	Amygdala Q1 Model 3 Assumption Right Activation Recall-Left Saccade	,708
	expressing arousal emotion	,000
	expressing arousal content	,232

a. Dependent Variable: Eye movement for emotions

Appendix X: Multiple Sclerosis' Frequencies

	Sex	Total number of expressed positive content	Total number of expressed negative content	Positive or Negative content-amygdala arousal	Eye Movement Direction Before Narrative
N Valid	6	6	6	6	6
Missing	0	0	0	0	0

	Stimuli Content	Emotions	Emotional thoughts direct Recall amygdala	NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade	NLP Assumption Recall-Left saccade
N Valid	6	6	6	6	6
Missing	0	0	0	0	0

	Object recognition direct recall hippocampus	Object location direct recall PFC	NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade	Existing cues	Eye movement for emotions
N Valid	6	6	6	6	6
Missing	0	0	0	0	0

	Eye movement content	NLP Assumption Construct-Right Saccade	Amygdala Emot Model 1 Assumption Left Arousal(POS/NEG)-Right Saccade	Amygdala Cont Model 1 Assumption Left Arousal(POS/NEG)-Right Saccade	Amygdala Q1 Model 2 Assumption Left Activation Recall-Right Saccade
N Valid	6	6	6	6	6
Missing	0	0	0	0	0

Statistics

		Amygdala Q1 Model 3 Assumption Right Activation Recall-Left Saccade	Total Number of Lessions	Number of Lessions in Amygdala	Number of Lessions in PFC	Number of Lessions in Hippocampus (Left)
N	Valid	6	6	6	6	6
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0

Frequency Table

Sex

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	female	6	100,0	100,0	100,0

Total number of expressed positive content

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	0	4	66,7	66,7	66,7
	1	2	33,3	33,3	100,0
	Total	6	100,0	100,0	

Total number of expressed negative content

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	3	50,0	50,0	50,0
2	2	33,3	33,3	83,3
4	1	16,7	16,7	100,0
Total	6	100,0	100,0	

Positive or Negative content-amygdala arousal

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Arousal	6	100,0	100,0	100,0

Eye Movement Direction Before Narrative

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Left	6	100,0	100,0	100,0

Stimuli Content

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Negative	3	50,0	50,0	50,0
	Both Negative and Positive Content	3	50,0	50,0	100,0
	Total	6	100,0	100,0	

Emotions

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	neutral	2	33,3	33,3	33,3
	Negative	4	66,7	66,7	100,0
	Total	6	100,0	100,0	

Emotional thoughts direct Recall amygdala

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Left	6	100,0	100,0	100,0

NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Associative- L	6	100,0	100,0	100,0

NLP Assumption Recall-Left saccade

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Associative- L	6	100,0	100,0	100,0

Object recognition direct recall hippocampus

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Left	6	100,0	100,0	100,0

Object location direct recall PFC

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Right	1	16,7	16,7	16,7
Left	5	83,3	83,3	100,0
Total	6	100,0	100,0	

NLP assumption Recall-Left saccade

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Non Associative- R or C	1	16,7	16,7	16,7
	Associative- L	5	83,3	83,3	100,0
	Total	6	100,0	100,0	

Existing cues

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Left	6	100,0	100,0	100,0

Eye movement for emotions

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Center-Neutral	2	33,3	33,3	33,3
	Right-Negative	2	33,3	33,3	66,7
	Left-Negative	2	33,3	33,3	100,0
	Total	6	100,0	100,0	

Eye movement content

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Right-Negative	2	33,3	33,3	33,3
Left-Negative	2	33,3	33,3	66,7
Right for Both Positive-Negative	1	16,7	16,7	83,3
Center for Both Positive-Negative	1	16,7	16,7	100,0
Total	6	100,0	100,0	

NLP Assumption Construct-Right Saccade

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Non Associative- L or C	6	100,0	100,0	100,0

Amygdala Emot Model 1 Assumption Left Arousal(POS/NEG)-Right Saccade

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Non Associative- L or C	4	66,7	66,7	66,7
Associative- R	2	33,3	33,3	100,0
Total	6	100,0	100,0	

Amygdala Cont Model 1 Assumption Left Arousal(POS/NEG)-Right Saccade

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Non Associative- L or C	3	50,0	50,0	50,0
	Associative- R	3	50,0	50,0	100,0
	Total	6	100,0	100,0	

Amygdala Q1 Model 2 Assumption Left Activation Recall-Right Saccade

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Non Associative- L or C	6	100,0	100,0	100,0

Amygdala Q1 Model 3 Assumption Right Activation Recall-Left Saccade

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Associative- L	6	100,0	100,0	100,0

Total Number of Lessons

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	7	1	16,7	16,7	16,7
	9	2	33,3	33,3	50,0
	12	1	16,7	16,7	66,7
	13	1	16,7	16,7	83,3
	16	1	16,7	16,7	100,0
	Total	6	100,0	100,0	

Number of Lessons in Amygdala

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	2	2	33,3	33,3	33,3
	3	1	16,7	16,7	50,0
	4	2	33,3	33,3	83,3
	5	1	16,7	16,7	100,0
	Total	6	100,0	100,0	

Number of Lessons in PFC

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	2	1	16,7	16,7	16,7
	3	2	33,3	33,3	50,0
	5	1	16,7	16,7	66,7
	6	1	16,7	16,7	83,3
	7	1	16,7	16,7	100,0
	Total	6	100,0	100,0	

Number of Lessons in Hippocampus (Left)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	2	3	50,0	50,0	50,0
	3	1	16,7	16,7	66,7
	5	1	16,7	16,7	83,3
	6	1	16,7	16,7	100,0
	Total	6	100,0	100,0	

Appendix XI: Multiple Sclerosis' Results

One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Number of Lessions in Amygdala	6	3,33	1,211	,494
Emotional thoughts direct Recall amygdala	6	2,00	,000 ^a	,000

a. t cannot be computed because the standard deviation is 0.

One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 0					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	
Number of Lessions in Amygdala	6,742	5	,001	3,333	2,06	

One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 0
	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference
	Upper
Number of Lesions in Amygdala	4,60

T-Test

One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Object recognition direct recall hippocampus	6	2,00	,000 ^a	,000
Number of Lessions in Hippocampus (Left)	6	3,33	1,751	,715

a. t cannot be computed because the standard deviation is 0.

One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 0					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	
Number of Lessions in Hippocampus (Left)	4,663	5	,006	3,333	1,50	

One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 0
	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference
	Upper
Number of Lesions in Hippocampus (Left)	5,17

T-Test

One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Object location direct recall PFC	6	1,83	,408	,167
Number of Lessons in PFC	6	4,33	1,966	,803

One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 0					95% Confidence Interval of the Difference
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Lower	
					Upper	
Object location direct recall PFC	11,000	5	,000	1,833	1,40	
Number of Lessons in PFC	5,398	5	,003	4,333	2,27	

One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 0	
	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
	Upper	Lower
Object location direct recall PFC	2,26	
Number of Lessons in PFC	6,40	

WORD COUNT STATEMENT

Word Count

Section	Word Count
Abstract	364
Introduction	4529
Methodology	1509
Results	2394
Discussion	1429
TOTAL	10225

Signed: _____

Date: _____